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Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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D4.6 REUSABLE MODEL & ANALYTICAL TOOLS: SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE 3

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Abstract: A description of the software demonstration for the components of the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer, which provides the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform, including the API Gateway / orchestrator and the built-in analytical tools.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ABSA	Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis
API	Application Programming Interface
DAA	Data Acquisition and Analytics
EC	European Commission
ELSA	Entity-level sentiment analysis
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
HDP	Hierarchical Dirichlet Process
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LSA	Latent Semantic Analysis
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
POS	Part-of-Speech
REST	Representational State Transfer
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SKA	Situational Knowledge Acquisition
SKA-EDA	Situational Knowledge Acquisition Exploratory Data Analysis
SKA-TSF	Situational Knowledge Acquisition Time Series Forecasting
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

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Executive Summary

This document is the third and last software demonstrator deliverable of PolicyCLOUD at M34, October 2022, of the project and is intended for the reviewers of the software deliverables.

This deliverable provides the description of the final software demonstrator for the components of the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer, which provides the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform. The components include the DAA API Gateway (responsible for the overall orchestration and the layer API), the built-in analytical tools such as the new Trend Analysis tool as well as the analytical tools already presented in D4.4 [6]: Data cleaning and interoperability, Situational Knowledge, Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis and Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data analysis, and the Operational Data Repository.

The full integration of the DAA API Gateway (responsible for the overall orchestration and the layer API) was demonstrated during the review of June 2021 for two use cases. As of the publication of this deliverable, this has been extended in multiple ways:

1. Additional ingest analytics capabilities such as Trend Analysis were added as detailed in section 2.1.3 and 2.1.4
2. The new integration of the Politika framework with PolicyCloud as detailed in section 2.2.5 of D4.5 [3] and as further detailed in sections 2.1.5.4 and 2.1.6 of this deliverable.
3. The integrated Politika framework was itself used for two use cases, as detailed in section 2.2.6.2

The novel seamless architecture which was introduced in D4.4 [6] and which presents single logical datasets to users that can be explored with SQL had further been enhanced in the past year by performance enhancements of the SQL JOIN as detailed in section 4.4.4 of D4.5.

The impact of using the seamless technology is minimal, as the users do not even know in what storage tier their datasets are stored. The only impact is a change of the SQL statement that now makes use of a *table function* that accepts standard SQL statements though, as detailed in section 2.2.8.3.

1. Introduction

1.1 Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer

The Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) layer is designed for extensibility and reusability of analytic functions. New analytics functions can be registered into PolicyCLOUD and reused for applying analytics on new and existing registered data sources. The detailed architecture and functionality are provided in D4.5 ‘Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Design and Open Specification 3’ [3]. Figure 1 provides the high-level architecture of the DAA layer, displaying the main components and the interactions with the various exploiters.

FIGURE 1 - DATA ACQUISITION AND ANALYTICS LAYER

The design is based on the serverless model, and more specifically on the open-source project Apache OpenWhisk¹, a distributed serverless platform, where functions are activated on demand, either directly through a PolicyCLOUD user request or by event/rule.

We differentiate between two main types of functions:

1. Analytic-ingest functions, used to apply initial analytic and/or transformation on the data fusion path of data sources.
2. Analytic functions, triggered by the PolicyCLOUD users through the Policy Layer. These functions perform an analysis on an (already ingested) specified data source to provide analytic insights needed for policy decisions

¹ <https://OpenWhisk.apache.org>

The DAA API Gateway component provides the external frontend of the DAA layer, as well as all required orchestration for the function and data source registrations and activation of the API. The other components are the built-in analytics functions for Data Cleaning and Interoperability, Situational Knowledge, Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis, and the Operational Data Repository component which is provided by the LeanXcale database. All these components (as well as the OpenWhisk cluster and the LeanXcale database) are running above a Kubernetes cluster. The engine of the Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data analysis component is running in standalone mode outside of the PolicyCLOUD platform; however it has been integrated within the PolicyCLOUD platform so that the users can now a) invoke a desired actions (such as a simulation) by specifying through the PDT its parameters b) visualise/analyse the output of these actions by using PolicyCLOUD analytics. This integration was done in a generic manner that fits other external frameworks. This is detailed in section 2.2.5 of D4.5 [\[3\]](#)

1.2 Summary of Changes: DAA Layer

Each of the components of the DAA layer has its specific summary of changes subsection. Therefore, we will here only mention the two major additions that occurred from D4.4 [\[6\]](#):

The DAA architecture was used to implement the integration of external frameworks such as the Politika framework as detailed in section 2.2.5 of D4.5 [\[3\]](#) and further detailed.

An important extension of the DAA, not reported into D4.5 [\[3\]](#) because it occurred just after, consists of adding a new type of data source, the “existing” data source. This extension was motivated by the fact that for many reasons, datasets may be ingested within the PolicyCLOUD storage without having been registered through the DAA. One such example is the fact that the LeanXcale company has implemented a client connector to the AWS GLUE analytic pipeline. We therefore have a situation where datasets may be directly ingested within the PolicyCLOUD datastore without being registered through the DAA.

This extension permits users to register with the DAA datasets that on the one hand are physically in the data store of PolicyCLOUD but which on the other hand are unknown to the DAA. After ingestion, ingest-analytic functions or analytic functions can be applied on these datasets.

As a global aspect, the DAA layer has been stable from the issuance of the PolicyCLOUD. D4.2 - Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 1 [\[5\]](#), however in this third version of the demonstrator, all components are now fully integrated.

2. Prototype overview

An initial standalone prototype comprising all the components with initial two end-to-end scenario demonstrations were performed during the review of June 2021. They demonstrated integrations of the developed software components where the data was streamed from the Gateway to the data storage through Apache Kafka and where the analytic-ingest functions were run over the Apache OpenWhisk framework.

Additional scenarios have been added and the various analytic components, including the Social Analytics component, are now applied to multiple additional scenarios. End-to-end integration and demonstration for these additional scenarios are delivered in the current last version of the software demonstrator.

The advanced analytic capabilities of the “Politika” software (Social Dynamics analytics component) are now integrated to the PolicyCLOUD platform. This permits Politika users to specify and launch Politika actions, such as simulations, and then to visualise them using the PolicyCLOUD analytic tools.

Figure 2 depicts the terrorist heatmap use case running in DAA. Once the dataset has been ingested, Heatmap analytic functions may be commanded to be applied on the dataset through the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT):

FIGURE 2 - GTD USE CASE

Figure 3 shows the Aragon use case, which uses a streaming dataset and a different ingest-analytics: Sentiment Analysis computation. It should be noted that the ingest-analytics pipeline may comprise multiple ingest-analytics as was performed for some of the other scenarios

FIGURE 3 - ARAGON USE CASE

2.1 Main components of the prototype

This section provides the description of the components included in the prototype.

2.1.1 DAA API Gateway

The DAA API Gateway developed in Task 4.1 is responsible for the orchestration and integration of all the components of the DAA layer (analytic functions, data sources, data repository) as well as providing the external interface for the layer's exploiters – analytic owners, data source owners, and the Policy layer (through which the end user apply desired analytics). Its full description can be found in section 2.1.2 of deliverable D4.5 [3]. Its roles include forming the proper setup of the registered analytic functions and data sources to ensure the correct data ingest process (applying the required ingest-time analytics/transformation – in Ingest-now, Streaming and Existing modes), and applying the requested analytics on the requested data source. The DAA API Gateway is implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk cluster), where the state is managed both on the OpenWhisk itself (e.g., analytic functions' metadata) and the database.

2.1.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.1.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The scope of the Data Cleaning component is to undertake all the processes regarding the data validation and data cleaning of all the incoming heterogeneous data, to the possible extent. The Data Cleaning component provides the interface that implements the data cleaning workflow as documented in deliverable D4.5 [3], to be utilized by the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components, ensuring data accuracy and consistency of the incoming datasets.

The updated architecture and design of the Data Cleaning component was documented in D4.5 with the purpose of addressing the volatility of the incoming data information to improve data accuracy, consistency, and completeness for the PolicyCLOUD platform. Thus, the Data Cleaning component implements all the processes that identify datasets that may contain inaccurate, incorrect, incomplete,

or irrelevant data elements and consequently replace, modify or delete these data elements safeguarding the reliability and appropriateness of the incoming data information. The software prototype of the Data Cleaning component was driven by this specification.

In this context, the Data Cleaning component is composed of one (1) main service, namely the `DataCleaningService`, which in turn consists of three (3) internal services: the `ValidationService`, the `CleaningService`, and the `VerificationService`. The main service, `DataCleaningService`, handles all the incoming and outgoing traffic of the DataCleaner component and is the only service exposed to the rest of the platform components. Contrary to the main service, the three (3) internal services are not exposed to the rest of the platform components, whereas the `DataCleaningService` is interacting with these services internally to realize the data cleaning workflow. The provided functionalities of the services are further depicted below.

- **DataCleaningService:** the main service of the Data Cleaning component in charge of executing the data cleaning workflow of PolicyCLOUD platform. Since the data cleaning workflow comprises several sequential steps, each one implemented by one of the internal services of the component, the `DataCleaningService` is responsible for the orchestration of these internal services as well as for monitoring their execution, and thus providing the execution results to the requestor. In addition to the data cleaning workflow execution, the `DataCleaningService` is responsible for the implementation of the single interface for data cleaning requests. In deeper detail, the `DataCleaningService` implements one (1) main function:
 - *initiateCleaning (dataset: File): Void.* This is the main function that initiates the `DataCleaningService`. It receives as input the provided dataset. This dataset is either already stored or still streaming and is in json format. It is responsible for orchestrating the rest of the internal services towards the execution of the data cleaning workflow.
- **ValidationService:** the internal service responsible for the data validation processing of the incoming data. The `ValidationService` performs a series of validation checks to evaluate the conformance to a set of constraints currently integrated in the business logic of the service. The current list of validation rules includes the following (regarding the historical data):
 - Conformance to specific data type.
 - Conformance to mandatory fields.
 - Conformance to specific value length.
 - Conformance to specific value representation.
 - Conformance to specific value range.
 - Identification of duplicate values for the data elements.
 - Identification of duplicate data elements.

It should be noted that the list of the validation rules will be furtherly enriched as the project evolves.

As for its provided functions, the `ValidationService` implements the following functions:

- *validateData(dataset: File): List.* This is the main function that initiates the `ValidationService`. It receives as an input the provided dataset (in json format), being responsible for identifying and returning the list of errors based on the evaluation of the

set of the constraints that have been set. To properly work, validateData exploits the following internal functions:

- *checkString(i: String): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkDecimal(d: Decimal): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkInt(i: Integer): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkMaxDigits(i: Numerical): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific value length.
- *checkRange(i: Numerical, j: Numerical): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific value range.

Based on the aforementioned, Figure 4 depicts a snapshot of an uploaded dataset containing historical data, prior to performing any cleaning action. It should be mentioned that for this dataset, a data schema has been already created including all the validation rules that each row and column of the dataset should obey to. What is more, it should be noted that this dataset refers to the scenario that regards the Participatory Policies Against Radicalization (Scenario #1.1), as it is documented in D2.2 [2].

eventid	year	imonth	iday	approxdatextended	resolutor	country	country_tiregion	region_txt	provstate	city	latitude	longitude	specificity	vicinity	location	summary
1.97E+11	1970	1	14	0		217	United Sts	1 North America	Illinois	Champaign	40,11675	-88,2393	1	0	Champaign	1/14/1970
1.97E+11	1970	1	15	0		218	Uruguay	3 South America	Montevideo	Montevideo	-34,8912	-56,1872	1	0		
1.97E+11	1970	1	19	0		217	United Sts	1 North America	Washington	Seattle	47,61079	-122,331	1	0	Seattle	Ur 1/17/1970

FIGURE 4 - SNAPSHOT OF GTD DATA

Similarly, Figure 5 depicts a snapshot of retrieved streaming Twitter data, prior to performing any cleaning action. It should be mentioned that this data refers to the scenario that regards the Intelligent Policies for The Denomination of Origin (Scenario #2.1), as documented in D2.6.

CF Illueca - CD Cariñena
Estadio "Papa Luna"
17:00 horas
Domingo 10 de octubre

La derrota del pasado domingo contra el Barbastro ya es historia. Nuestros jugadores ya están de pie, nuestro equipo ya se ha puesto el mono de faena para resarcirse de ese traspies. <https://t.co/Nn16g9p9Je>

FIGURE 5 - SNAPSHOT OF TWITTER DATA

- **CleaningService**: It is the internal service responsible for the cleaning of the incoming data. The CleaningService eliminates the list of errors identified by the ValidationService by applying all the necessary corrective actions on the data elements marked with errors. Cleaning is performed automatically based on a set of actions currently integrated in the business logic of the component. The current list of possible cleaning actions includes the following:

For stored data:

- Deletion (drop) of the complete record (row).
- Replacement of data element's value with the mean value.

- Replacement of data element's value with the maximum value.
- Replacement of data element's value with the minimum value.
- Replacement of data element's value with the most frequent value.

For streaming data:

- Use of NLP processes.

It should be noted that the list of the cleaning actions will be furtherly enriched as the project evolves.

The CleaningService implements the following functions:

- *cleanHistoricalData(errors: List, dataset: File): File*: This is the main function that initiates the CleaningService when receiving historical data. It receives as an input the provided dataset (in json format), as well as the identified list of errors produced by the ValidationService, being responsible for constructing and returning the cleaned dataset. In order to properly work, cleanHistoricalData exploits the following internal functions:
 - *dropRow(row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function rejecting the complete record (row).
 - *replaceWithMean(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the mean value.
 - *replaceWithMax(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the maximum value.
 - *replaceWithMinimum(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the minimum value.
 - *replaceWithMostFrequent(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the most frequent value.
- *cleanStreamingData(dataset: File): File*: is the main function that initiates the CleaningService when receiving streaming data. It receives as an input the provided data (in json format), responsible for constructing and returning the cleaned dataset. In order to properly work, cleanStreamingData exploits the following internal functions:
 - *removeEmojis(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any emojis that exist in the data.
 - *removeStopwords(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any stopwords that exist in the data.
 - *removePunctuations(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any punctuations that exist in the data.
 - *removeMention(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any mentions that exist in the data.
 - *removeHashtag(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any hashtags that exist in the data.

Based on the aforementioned, in the provided example of the historical data (GTD), the row with the identified error (null value) has been dropped (Figure 6). This was requested by the cleaning

actions of the specific Scenario, where it was described that in the case that a null value would appear, then the overall row containing this null value should be deleted.

eventid	year	month	day	approxdate	extended	resolution	country	country_tregion	region_txt	provstate	city	latitude	longitude	specificity	vicinity	location	summary
1,97E+11	1970	1	14			0	217 United Stc	1 North America		Illinois	Champaign	40,11675	-88,2393	1	0	Champaign	1/14/1970
1,97E+11	1970	1	19			0	217 United Stc	1 North America		Washingt	Seattle	47,61079	-122,331	1	0	Seattle Ur	1/17/1970

FIGURE 6 - SNAPSHOT OF THE CLEANED DATASET

Regarding the collected streaming (Twitter) data, all the needed cleaning corrections were applied, removing in this case all the emojis, stopwords, punctuations, mentions, and tags that existed in the ingested data (Figure 7).

```
CF Illueca CD Cariñena Estadio " Papa Luna " 17 00 horas Domingo 10 octubre La derrota pasado domingo Barbastro historia Nue-
tros jugadores pie equipo puesto mono faena resarcirse traspiés
```

FIGURE 7 - SNAPSHOT OF THE CLEANED DATASET

- VerificationService:** is the internal service responsible for the verification and evaluation of the corrective actions undertaken by the CleaningService, aiming at ensuring the accuracy and the consistency of the updated incoming data according to the PolicyCLOUD platform requirements. In more detail, the VerificationService implements the following main function:
 - verifyData(): List:* the main function that initiates the VerificationService. It receives as input the provided dataset (in json format), the cleaned dataset (in json format), as well as the identified list of errors, being responsible for the final verification and evaluation of the corrective actions in combination with the actual cleaned dataset, and thus outputting the results of the evaluation. In case that no corrective action is needed, a null list is returned. Otherwise, the VerificationService returns a list of additional corrective actions that should be done once or repetitively by the CleaningService.

Based on the aforementioned, in the two (2) provided examples, the VerificationService checks and confirms that the CleaningService has successfully performed all the required cleaning actions, returning a null List since no further corrective actions are needed to take place.

2.1.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

Under the scope of this Deliverable, the 2nd Software Prototype of Enhanced Interoperability component consists of several sub-tasks, which are further separated into different layers of the overall proposed pipeline which also introduced in the D4.5 [3]. The initial design of these layers, which integrate Semantic Web technologies with Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies and tasks, includes complete workflows and pipelines for annotating cleaned data, which are being sent into the Enhanced Interoperability Component from the Data Cleaning Component. Moreover, as also introduced in the D4.5 through these coupled technologies and methods, the Enhanced Interoperability Component seeks to provide a state-of-the-art approach to achieve interoperability in the data-driven policymaking domain. Introduced in D4.5, SemAI entitles this proposed hybrid approach and is a combination of commonly used semantic techniques coupled with the utilization of NLP tasks and methods. The latter is being implemented and used from the early beginning steps of the Enhanced Interoperability Component. To this end, the main functionality of the first sub-component of the Enhanced

Interoperability component, that is introduced under the scope of this 2nd Software Prototype, is to annotate cleaned data with URIs pointing to corresponding Wikidata and DBPedia² entities & proper Ontologies, by utilizing SemAI techniques. On top of this, the final extraction of this sub-component is URI annotated data in JSON format. To this end, the system will be able to automatically integrate data from different sources by replacing the context-dependent keys in the JSON output with URIs pointing to semantic vocabularies that will be used to represent and link the data [12].

Furthermore, as analysed in D4.5 after fetching cleaned data from the Data Cleaning Component, the Enhanced Interoperability Component seeks to implement the hybrid approach of SemAI through two core subtasks/sub-components: the Linguistic & Semantic Analysis with NLP (1st sub-component) and the Ontology Mapping (2nd sub-component).

To exploit what the SemAI offers, data has first to be structured and annotated. To this end, in the first sub-component presented and introduced in this Deliverable, cleaned data will be analyzed, transformed, and annotated with appropriate URI metadata using Semantic Web technologies and NLP tasks, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Part-of-Speech Tagging (POS Tagging) and Named Entity Linking (NEL). These coupled functionalities are being used into three different layers/steps of the overall sub-component as introduced below. Moreover, semantic and syntactic URI annotated data are interlinked through the Ontology Mapping task. The overall Interoperability component is further enhanced and completed by the Ontology Mapping mechanism, where a Topic Detection and Annotation sub-component detects the topic of the given data and afterwards an Ontology Mapping and structuring mechanism are used to interlink not only URI annotated data with proper ontologies, but also to interlink and correlate datasets among them.

On top of this, more concrete examples and details are given below for some of the core functionalities/services that are implemented under the scope of these two sub-components. To this end, below are the outcomes of some core sub-tasks for these two sub-components. In the scope of the below demonstration tweets for the Aragon Use Case that were fetched from the Cloud Gateways and APIs component of the PolicyCLOUD project were processed.

- **POS Tagging:** POS tagging task is used after Tokenization and sentence splitting tasks. The part-of-speech tagger is responsible to assign to each token an extended POS tag and to identify its role and usage in the text. Following is an example of the outcome of the POS tagging task that was implemented on a raw sentence.

² https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

```
[(x.orth_,x.pos_, x.lemma_) for x in [y
                                     for y
                                     in nlp_es(str(article_spanish))
                                     if not y.is_stop and y.pos_ != 'PUNCT']]

('Cariñena', 'PROPN', 'Cariñena'),
('8', 'NUM', '8'),
('0', 'NUM', '0'),
('1', 'NUM', '1'),
('Edición', 'PROPN', 'Edición'),
('limitada', 'ADJ', 'limitar'),
('C', 'PROPN', 'C'),
('Souvignon', 'PROPN', 'Souvignon'),
('2014', 'NUM', '2014'),
('Merlot', 'PROPN', 'Merlot'),
('2015', 'NUM', '2015'),
('Syrah', 'PROPN', 'Syrah'),
('2016', 'NUM', '2016'),
('empujar', 'VERB', 'empujar'),
('migas', 'NOUN', 'migar'),
('calcando', 'VERB', 'calcar'),
('fresco', 'ADJ', 'fresco'),
('hoyRT', 'PROPN', 'hoyRT'),
...]
```

```
[(x.orth_,x.pos_, x.lemma_) for x in [y
                                     for y
                                     in nlp_en(str(article_english))
                                     if not y.is_stop and y.pos_ != 'PUNCT']]

[('', 'VERB', ''),
 ('s', 'VERB', 's'),
 ('winewednesday', 'PROPN', 'winewednesday'),
 ('calls', 'VERB', 'call'),
 ('bottle', 'NOUN', 'bottle'),
 ('2017', 'NUM', '2017'),
 ('Embruix', 'PROPN', 'Embruix'),
 ('Vall', 'PROPN', 'Vall'),
 ('Llach', 'PROPN', 'Llach'),
 ('Garnacha', 'PROPN', 'Garnacha'),
 ('Merlot', 'PROPN', 'Merlot'),
 ('Syrah', 'PROPN', 'Syrah'),
 ('Cariñena', 'PROPN', 'Cariñena'),
 ('Cabernet', 'PROPN', 'Cabernet'),
 ('Sauvignon', 'PROPN', 'Sauvignon'),
 ('Priorat', 'PROPN', 'Priorat'),
 ('Spain', 'PROPN', 'Spain'),
```

FIGURE 8 - POS TAGGING

- NER Task:** Named Entity Recognition (NER) task is the process of classifying named entities found in a text into predefined categories, such as persons, places, organizations, dates, etc. To this end, spaCy and its built-in functions are being utilized. In addition, this specific NLP subtask is being utilized for both the English and Spanish languages, hence the respective NLP pipelines provided by spaCy are being used for these specific languages. More specifically, for the English language the *en_core_web_sm* package has been downloaded and used, which is one of spaCy's English tokenizers, taggers, parsers and NER pipelines and tools. In addition, concerning the Spanish language the *es_core_news_md* pipeline has been downloaded and used, which is the respective version of spaCy's NLP pipelines for the Spanish language. On top of this, spaCy uses a statistical model to classify a broad range of entities, including persons, events, locations, dates, cardinals, nationalities / religions among other entities. Moreover, *displacy* has been used to visualize the outcomes of this subtask, as it is spaCy's built-in named entity visualizer that allows checking the model's predictions. Following is an example of the NER task implemented on raw text.

FIGURE 9 - NER TASK

- Ontology-based NER:** As introduced in section 3.2.3 of D4.5, to further enhance the generalization of the NER task, an ontology-based NER approach has also been followed and implemented. The ontologies that are used to train the NER task and finally provide the proper URIs to the identified entities can either be introduced by the policymaker, or widely applied ontologies can be used. The overall functionality of this task is summarized as follows. The NER performs tasks to locate nouns in the sentences based on the output of the spaCy Part-Of-Speech Tagger, then the identified nouns are lemmatized with the lemmatizer available in WordNetLemmatizer provided by the [nltk](#) library. Furthermore, SPARQL is used to further annotate the identified and lemmatized nouns with either URIs derived from the given ontology or from widely used ontologies and knowledge bases, such as the Wikidata. Hence, the final recognized entities are linked with specific identifiers to facilitate their utilization and analysis by the analytical components of the PolicyCLOUD project. As a result, this integrated and hybrid approach ultimately leads to a powerful and better Enhanced Interoperability Component for achieving and providing an enhanced interlinking between divergent data and datasets. This approach is highly utilized especially on tweets the usage of a domain-specific ontology the system permits to recognize domain-related entities from large numbers of user messages from Twitter. In addition, and based on all the aforementioned functionalities and implementations, the Enhanced Interoperability component can be applied to each new use case and dataset. A typical example of the output of this subtask indicating the entity annotations of the ontology-based and domain-specific entity recognizer is presented below in Figure 10 , where the component has

been utilized on twitter data with regards to the Scenario B Opinion on social networks of the SARGA use case as presented in D6.11.

```
{
  "created_at": "2022-09-10T10:38:01.000Z",
  "id": "1570723074008821701",
  "id_str": "1570723074008821701",
  "text": "After the ideal glass for #GrenacheDay?\n\n
    :   \"Our Riedel Winewings Syrah Glass is the perfect choice\"
    :   \"for accentuating your Grenache's bold, fruity aromas.\n\n\"
    :   \"Get yours today at https://t.co/jc1CbyGBs0. https://t.co/RBCq9G4hK\",
  "entities": {
    "annotations": [
      {
        "entity_recognizer": [
          {
            "start": 51,
            "end": 62,
            "label": "Syrah",
            "iri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#EstecilloSyrahLegado",
            "typeURI": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#RedWine",
            "type": "PRODUCT"
          },
          {
            "start": 91,
            "end": 99,
            "label": "Grenache",
            "iri": "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q390242",
            "type": "PRODUCT"
          },
          {
            "start": 123,
            "end": 128,
            "label": "today",
            "iri": "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3151090",
            "type": "DATE"
          }
        ]
      }
    ],
    "hashtags": [
      {
        "start": 20,
        "end": 38,
        "tag": "GrenacheDay"
      }
    ],
    "urls": [
      {
        "start": 170,
        "end": 193,
        "url": "https://t.co/jc1CbyGBs0",
        "expanded_url": "https://www.riedel.com/en-gb/shop/riedel-winewings/syrah-shiraz-123400041",
        "display_url": "riedel.com/en-gb/shop/rie...",
        "images": [
          {
            "url": "https://pbs.twimg.com/news_img/1570723079060855943/qF-HygCF?format=png&name=orig",
            "width": 1200,
            "height": 630
          },
          {
            "url": "https://pbs.twimg.com/news_img/1570723079060855943/qF-HygCF?format=png&name=150x150",
            "width": 150,
            "height": 150
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "start": 195,
        "end": 218,
        "url": "https://t.co/RBCq9G4hK",
        "expanded_url": "https://twitter.com/RiedelUK/status/1570723074008821701/photo/1",
        "display_url": "pic.twitter.com/RBCq9G4hK",
        "media_key": "3_1570723071605395457"
      }
    ]
  },
  "geo": null,
  "retweet_count": 0,
  "favorite_count": 0,
  "lang": "en"
}
```

FIGURE 10 – ONTOLOGY-BASED ENTITY RECOGNIZER OUTPUT EXAMPLE

- **JSON URI annotated sentence:** The final step of the provided sub-component is the extraction of the URI annotated text in JSON format. To this end, SPARQL query language was used to interlink identified entities from the raw text with Wikidata entities. On top of this, DBpedia Spotlight tool is used for interlinking and URI annotating text entities with DBpedia entities. A typical example of the code which performs the SPARQL query to the Wikidata knowledge base is presented below in Figure 11.

```
for sent in doc.sents:
    labels = list()
    for e in sent.ents:
        sparql = """SELECT ?item WHERE { ?item rdfs:label '%s@en }""" % (e.text)
        res = return_sparql_query_results(sparql)
        labels.append({e.text, e.start_char, e.end_char, e.label_, res["results"]["bindings"][0]["item"]["value"]})
    djson.append({'text': sent.text, "labels": labels})
```

FIGURE 11 – CODE FOR SPARQL QUERY

Following is the final outcome of a URI annotated sentence:

```
[
  {
    "text": "Campo de Cariñena Lanza un vino dedicado a Joaquín Carbonell.",
    "labels": [
      [
        {0, 17, "LOCATION", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1031448", "Campo de Cariñena"},
        {43, 60, "PERSON", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q9012220", "Joaquín Carbonell"}
      ]
    ]
  },
  {
    "text": "La recaudación obtenida en La venta de esta edición limitada a 500 botellas será en beneficio de La Asociación Cultural Joaquín Carbonell\n\nhttps://t.co/wPURQq8Eka en @periodicoaragon",
    "labels": [
      [
        {125, 128, "CARDINAL", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23610", "500"}
      ]
    ]
  }
]
[
  {
    "text": "For the whole month of October try a glass of 2019 La Cappuccina Soave for $8 or a bottle for $24, or try a bottle of 2017 Embruix de Vall Llach [Garnacha, Merlot, Syrah, Cariñena, Cabernet Sauvignon] for only $60!",
    "labels": [
      [
        {46, 50, "DATE", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25274", "2019"},
        {76, 77, "NUMBER", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23348", "8"},
        {95, 97, "MONEY", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23857", "24"},
        {118, 122, "DATE", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25290", "2017"},
        {156, 162, "ORG", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q213338", "Merlot"},
        {164, 169, "PERSON", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q332720", "Syrah"},
        {171, 179, "ORG", "http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q984529", "Cariñena"}
      ]
    ]
  },
  {
    "text": "Book your reservation below! \n\n",
    "labels": []
  }
],
```

```

    {"text": "https://t.co/DXUMdgHdLH https://t.co/wL2UILxJee",
      "labels": []
    }
  ]

```

- Topic Identification:** Alongside the semantic annotation of the data, the SemAI hybrid mechanism provides a topic annotation to the original dataset. The latter is achieved by using subtask of Topic Identification or Topic Modelling. To this end, the component introduces a solution of dataset interoperability in order to better identify interlinking and correlations between different datasets. For this specific subtask three (3) different models were utilized in order to identify the most appropriate topic identification algorithm for the Aragon use case as implemented in corresponding tweets under the scope of this specific scenario. More specifically, these three (3) topics modelling algorithms were the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [11], the Latent semantic analysis (LSA) [10], and the Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP) [9]. For selecting and evaluating these models, the topic coherence coefficient was selected as a comparison measure [8]. In general, good topics are considered topics that can be described by a short label, therefore this is what the topic coherence measure should capture, so the best models achieve highest topic coherence scores.

FIGURE 12 - TOPIC MODELS COHERENCES

Figure 12 shows that the HDP model provides the best definition and identification as it has the highest coherence among the three (3) examined models. Hence, the topics of this model will be selected as the final topics with which the corresponding dataset will be tagged and annotated.

- Ontology Mapping:** The approach being followed in the Ontology Mapping subtask is to utilize a Python driver that initializes the connection with the Neo4j graph database. Neo4j has been selected as it is a native graph database, built from the ground up to leverage not only data but also data semantic and syntactic relationships. To this end, the SemAI mechanism will be able to store all the cleaned tweet text to Neo4j. Having already performed the entity extraction, entity linking and the topic identification algorithms on the text of each tweet, it is then feasible for the

system to save the tweet text, tweet id, and all the extracted entities to a JSON file that can then be used to save and update the Neo4j graph, and to extend the data model through the connection and interlinking of the Tweet nodes with new Entities, such as Persons, Locations, and Organizations, as also to newly created Topic nodes as identified by the previous subtasks of NER, Ontology-based NER and Topic Identification. To better highlight the utilization and importance of this subtask of the Enhanced Interoperability component the below Figure 13 depicts a graph visualization of processed and interoperable tweets that can be further utilized to enhance the knowledge that can be derived from these tweets and their correlation with data derived from other datasets, performing the appropriate queries and linking. These tweets have been annotated with appropriate entities which are further interlinked either with the domain-based ontology provided by the data provider, such as the “Syrah” product which has been linked with the URI <http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#EstecilloSyrahLegado> , or with widely known knowledge based, i.e., Wikidata, such as the Grenache product which has been interlinked with the URI <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q390242>. These two entities can be found in the “entity-recognizer” key of Figure 10. The Ontology Mapping performs the mapping between all the different instances that are correlated with the same attributes, entities etc. For instance, Figure 13 depicts two correlated tweets, annotated both with the recognized entity “Syrah” which is further mapped via its appropriate IRI to the Ontology that has been provided by the data provider.

FIGURE 13 - TWEETS CORRELATION VIA ANNOTATED ENTITY

2.1.2.3 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY AND DATA CLEANING

In this Deliverable and on contrary to D4.4 [6], the updated architecture of the Data Cleaning component has been applied and validated in both stored data and streaming (Twitter) data, verifying the successful applicability of the Data Cleaning component in both cases. Furthermore, the Data Cleaning component

has been redesigned and implemented in a more dynamic way so that its execution only requires data and no longer the corresponding data schemas defined by the Use Case partners. In the updated version of the component, the data schema is automatically created by the developed mechanism, and then used for the cleaning process.

Regarding Enhanced Interoperability, the overall workflow of the Enhanced Interoperability component is being utilized and introduced as in the context of D4.4 [6]. In addition to what was presented in D4.4, in this deliverable the Ontology-based NER subtask has been introduced. The ontology-based manual annotation indicates that it is possible to perform high-quality annotation despite the complexity of different domain-specific terminologies and the lack of context in tweets. Furthermore, to further highlight the importance of the Ontology Mapping subtask within the Enhanced Interoperability component, a concrete example based on processed and annotated Twitter data is being presented in the context of this deliverable.

2.1.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

2.1.3.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS CONDUCTED BY DATA VISUALIZATION

For this last release the situational knowledge acquisition and analysis (SKA) task has been focused on providing the final version of the Exploratory Data Analysis tool (SKA-EDA) applied to all the use cases, in particular applied to (*citing section 4.1.3.1 of D4.5*):

- *Use Case 1 (Participatory policies against Radicalization). More specifically to “Scenario A: Radicalization Incidents” interested in monitoring the occurrence of radicalization incidents in a given area.*
- *Use case 2 (Intelligent policies for agri-food industry). More specifically to “Scenario A - Sales prices datasets”, the policymaker can monitor the sale price of wine as specified in different specialized websites*
- *Use Case 3 (Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis). More specifically to the “Scenario A: Visualization” interested in obtaining diverse visualizations of the data received with regards to 6 different sectors (Road Infrastructure, Environment and Air Quality, Waste Collection and Waste Disposal, Transport and Parking, Cleanliness of Public Spaces, Violation of Public Order). Optionally, SKA-EDA might be used for “Scenario C: Environment and Air Quality Cross Analysis” focused on providing cross-analysis between the data coming from the Sofia Call Center and data from the air quality sensors in the city.*

In our case, due to the nature of the managed datasets and the scenarios raised for the PolicyCLOUD use cases, this SKA-EDA tool is focused on providing exploration of datasets based on descriptive analysis conducted by data visualization. Thus, the SKA-EDA is an exploratory data analysis tool in charge of collecting datasets, applying some transformations, performing some computations and providing different json results to be plotted by the visualization components (addressed in Work package 6). In

particular, and as it was fully described in D4.5, the core of the SKA-EDA tool provides a REST API for a set of variable distributions (*citing section 4.1.3.1 of D4.5*):

- *Uni-Frequency distribution: Frequency of occurrence for a single variable*
- *Bi-Frequency distribution: Frequency of occurrence for two variables*
- *Geographical distribution: Graphical representation of the number of events that happen in the specific geographical positions*
- *Accumulated distribution: Sum the value of a specific numeric variable across several categories.*
- *Temporal Evolution: List of values of a specific numeric variable across several categories*

See deliverables D4.4 [6] and D4.5 [3] for additional details of this tool.

2.1.3.2 PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS

In addition to the SKA-EDA component, this last version of the task also releases a new tool, SKA-TSF, in charge of applying stochastic-based techniques for forecasting univariate time series datasets. This tool is applied to the following use case (*citing section 4.1.3.2 of D4.5*):

- *“Use Case 3: Urban policymaking through analysis of crowdsourced data” (Scenario B- Supervised Predictive Analysis), the policymaker will be able to predict the number of incidents based on the SOFIA Call Center, will be provided. In particular, at the closure of this document, the time series forecasting tool is designed to predict the number of road infrastructure incidents based on the “Road Infrastructure” dataset provided by the use case. See below an example of the raw dataset.*

category_id	category	type_id	type_description	signal_id	timestamp	description	short_description	location	address	...	city
0	3	Пътна инфраструктура	Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти	1916	2015-01-03 16:50:29.220	<p>На кръстовището на ул. "Чукар" и ...	Много опасни шахти със счупени капаци!!!	POINT (23.2608783245087 42.6521040288064)	улица „Чукар“ 25-А, 1616 София, България	...	София
1	3	Пътна инфраструктура	Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти	1932	2015-01-04 17:06:32.915	<p>Счупена шахта.</p>	Счупена шахта	POINT (23.3194296061993 42.6900307803128)	булевард „Витоша“ 61, 1000 София, България	...	София
2	3	Пътна инфраструктура	Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти	1968	2015-01-06 13:22:14.792	<p>На тротоара на ъгъла на бул. Бъкстон и лока...	Счупен капак на шахта	POINT (23.2793244123786 42.6753331358636)	булевард „цар Борис III“ 155, 1618 София, Бълг...	...	София
3	3	Пътна инфраструктура	Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти	1982	2015-01-07 10:41:40.265	NaN	Липсващ капак на шахта	POINT (23.2465794682503 42.6891440458413)	улица „Феникс“ 33-б, 1632 София, България	...	София
4	3	Пътна инфраструктура	Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти	1986	2015-01-07 11:24:01.245	<p>На тротоара липсва капак на шахта и се виж...	липсващ капак на шахта	POINT (23.3397662 42.6959855)	улица „Сан Стефано“ 2, 1504 София, България	...	София

FIGURE 14 - USE CASE 3 ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE DATASET SAMPLE

The SKA-TSF tool have been developed following a common life cycling learning model procedure, consisting of the following steps (*citing section 4.1.3.2. of D4.5*):

1. *Dataset pre-processing: Univariate time series exploring and transformation*
2. *Parameter estimation: Time series component decomposition and analysis which support the model selection and configuration (selection of the hyperparameters)*
3. *Model training: Fitting the model with the best parameters and for a specific training set*
4. *Predicting outcomes: Forecasting new data with a pre-trained model*
5. *Deploy the model and integration into a full-grown system*

The raw "Road Infrastructure" dataset is transformed (step 1) from a dataset of 37370 entries and 26 columns into a univariate time series just with two variables: ds: the timestamp (set as index) and y: counter of incidents. This time serialised Road Infrastructure dataset is used for the Parameter Estimation (step 2) and Model training (step 3).

After the Time series component decomposition and analysis (step 2), two models were selected to be used in PolicyCLOUD. These are:

- **Prophet³** for its seasonality and trend management.

After analysing the Road Infrastructure timeseries and get familiarised with the Prophet model, some experiments were done for adjusting the Prophet parameters, giving as a result following "by-default" parameters (please, bear in mind these parameters and metrics attend the Road Infrastructure dataset used as training dataset at the closure of this document):

- seasonality_prior_scale=1.0
- holidays_prior_scale=0.1
- seasonality(name='yearly', period=365, fourier_order=3)
- seasonality(name='weekly', period=7, fourier_order=20)
- add_country_holidays(country_name='BG')

Throwing following Prophet performance in terms of metrics and graphs for a horizon of 30 days:

- Mean Squared Error (MSE) is 61.968253333838945
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is 5.531350373526993
- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is 7.871991700569745

³ <https://facebook.github.io/prophet/>

FIGURE 15 - OBSERVED AND ONE-STEP AHEAD FORECASTED VALUES USING PROPHET MODEL

- **Seasonal Arima⁴** for being one of the most widely used approaches

After analysing the time serialised Road Infrastructure timeseries and get familiarised with the Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) model, some experiments were done, and some tools were used (autoARIMA⁵) for adjusting the SARIMA parameters, giving as a result following “by-default” parameters (please, bear in mind these parameters and metrics attend the Road Infrastructure dataset used as training dataset at the closure of this document):

- orderBest = (5, 1, 5) → extracted from autorima[x] w/o seasonality
- seasonal_orderBest = (1, 0, 1, 7) → extracted manually checking documentation and ACF plot

Throwing following SARIMA performance in terms of metrics and graph for a startDate: 2020-05-01 00:00:00 and endDate: 2020-05-30 00:00:00:

- MSE is 58.07056845542988
- MAE is 5.047550262778151
- RMSE is 7.62040474354413

⁴ <https://otexts.com/fpp2/seasonal-arima.html>

⁵ https://alkaline-ml.com/pmdarima/modules/generated/pmdarima.arima.auto_arima.html

FIGURE 16 - OBSERVED AND ONE-STEP AHEAD FORECASTED VALUES USING SEASONAL ARIMA MODEL

In terms of services, the SKA_TSF tool basically consists of a set of REST services that allow on one hand the data sciences training two well-known models for forecasting time series (step 3) and on the other hand permits policymakers to make use of these trained models for predicting new outcomes (step 4). The prediction result is a json format file, containing both historical data and predicted data, to be plotted in the visualization components (addressed in Work package 6). In particular, the core of the SKA-TSF tool provides REST API for the following services (*citing D4.5*):

- *Training Service: A process for fitting a specific model for a specific training dataset and based on a pre-determine hyperparameters. In summary, this process retrieves a (training) dataset, based on the name passed as input parameter, performs the needed transformations and finally configures and fitting a particular model with concrete hyper-parameters*
- *Predicting Service: Based on a selected trained model, given the name/id as parameter, the process is able to return predicted values (in the form of a json file) for a horizon forecast passed as input. It's worth mentioning that the predicting process will throw reliable outcomes for the future within the next 6 months from the last period (in our case, last day) of the trained dataset used in the selected model. Therefore, it is up to the user the responsibility of keeping the model freshly re-trained with recent data for obtaining optimal results close to recent days.*

See deliverables D4.5 for more details on this tool.

2.1.3.3 SUMMARY OF CHANGE: SITUATIONAL KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION & ANALYSIS

This last release is focused on enhancing the exploratory data analysis in the PolicyCLOUD project by:

- enlarging the planned functionality, in the context of SKA-EDA in PolicyCLOUD, by introducing (categorical) temporal evolution of variables.
- implementing part of the Use Case 3: Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data, in particular Scenario B- Supervised Predictive Analysis
- integration of both SKA-EDA and SKA-TSF tools into:
 - the WP4 pipelines based on OpenWhisk,
 - PolicyCLOUD storage
 - visualisation components

2.1.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

For this third release, the functionality provided from this task is a new version of the sentiment analysis core component described and provided in D4.1 [11] and D4.2 [5]. While initial versions were focused on a document-level approach, *“the document contains an opinion on one main object expressed by the author of the document”* [12], this latest version will be based on an entity-level sentiment analysis (ELSA) approach [13], [15], [7] in charge of providing *“author sentiment towards various entities in text”* as cited in [14], which can be considered as an intermediate granularity between sentence-level sentiment, *“It’s known that the entity discussed in the sentence and there is just one single opinion in each sentence”* and aspect-level sentiment *“people talk about entities that have many aspects (attributes) and they have a different opinion about each of the aspects”*.

It will cover the analytical part of the Scenario B from UC#2 (“Intelligent policies for the development of denomination of origin”) which aim to get the positive, negative and neutral opinions about different wine related entities based on social media data. Additionally, this can also be applied to the Scenario C from UC#1 (“Participatory policies against Radicalization”) aiming to analyse the opinions in messages related to radicalization.

A Named-entity recognition process will be performed as first steps in the ELSA. This process will help for the entity identification, which then will be scored with polarity, and it will be of the Enhanced Interoperability component following an ontology -based approach.

2.1.4.1 ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

This analytical component has been implemented to provide indicators describing the sentiment of a text regarding a series of items or entities that are mentioned in that text. This process is done by means of the usage of the ABSA library⁶, which performs the aforementioned analysis by means of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. During the development of this last release, the following use cases were taken into account:

- Use Case 1 (“Participatory policies against Radicalization”): The ELSA is used in the scenario D (“Assessment of online propaganda”) to determine the sentiment regarding a series of entities recognized related with the radicalization scenario.
- Use case 2 (“Intelligent policies for the development of denomination of origin”): In this use case, the ELSA is applied in scenario B (“Opinions on social media”) in order to assess the sentiment of the different wine related entities in social media.

To give support to the scenarios described, two main components are the core of this analytical tool:

- The first core component of this analytical tool is the ELSA component, offered as a service, that, receiving a text and a series of entities that are mentioned in the text, computes the sentiment towards those entities in the present text, returning sentiment-based indicators for each one of the entities identified in the text.

⁶ <https://github.com/ScalaConsultants/Aspect-Based-Sentiment-Analysis>

- The second core component is the aggregator, this one serves as the main data serving service for the visualisations proposed in these scenarios. By means of this component, different sentiment-based data is aggregated according to different criteria (i.e., temporal, geographical, etc.) to offer a summary of the evolution of the sentiment indicators related to a given entity.

2.1.4.2 TREND ANALYSIS

The Trend Analysis component has been developed to provide further information regarding the presence of different entities in social media. In this sense, the core of this analytic is focused on the appearance over time of mentions to entities related to the use cases where this analytic is used. Additionally, this analytical component considers the relations between different entities from the use case, to generate some indicators of the importance based on the indirect presence in social media of different entities from the use case. It is important to also notice the requirement of a data source that provides the modelization of the scenario so this tool can make use of the relations between the different entities that take part in the scenario. This analytical tool has been developed for its application in the following use cases:

- Use Case 1 (“Participatory policies against Radicalization”): Scenario C (“Trend Analysis”) will make use of this analytical tool to identify which elements related to radicalization organizations are more present in social media, as well as the elements whose presence rises or falls on certain time windows.
- Use case 2 (“Intelligent policies for the development of denomination of origin”): A similar approach is followed in the scenario C (“Trend Analysis”), where the presence of elements related with the wineries is analysed in order to provide indicators on the most popular wines, wineries or regions, allowing to compare the popularity of these entities as well as see the entities with a higher increase of mentions and those that tend to appear less in a given time window.

The logic of this tool is structured around three different components:

- Conceptualizer: Is responsible to enrich the data coming from the social media texts and explicit mentions identified to see to which elements of the use case are linked those elements mentioned in each text. To perform this task, the conceptualizer takes advantage of the modelling provided by each use case (as an ontology or taxonomy) where the different elements that form the use case are defined as well as their relations.
- Tag cloud component: This component provides indicators of the presence of the different elements related to the use case in social media texts in a given time window. This component allows to evaluate and compare the presence of elements of the same type (e.g., compare the presence of the different wineries) in social media texts or allows to evaluate the presence of elements related to a given element (e.g. compare the presence of all the wines produced by a given winery) in social media texts between other possible analysis.
- Bursty concept: This component is responsible to highlight the elements whose presence has variated (raised or fallen) the most, comparing their presence in two time windows.

2.1.4.3 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPINION MINING & SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

During the third release of the analytics components here presented, the following changes have been introduced to give support to the functionalities of the different use cases of the POLICYCLOUD project:

- Trend analysis tool has been designed to give support to the different scenarios that will make use of it.
- The different modelling of the data required for the trend analysis tool has been proposed and implemented.
- The different components of the trend analysis tool (i.e., conceptualizer, tag cloud generator and bursty concept) have been developed and implemented as services to be offered by an API.
- The ELSA component of the sentiment analysis tool has been developed to provide the sentiment annotation of an element regarding a text provided.
- The sentiment aggregation from the sentiment analysis tool has been updated to provide all the sentiment data generated by the ELSA.

2.1.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

We describe the third prototype for the Social Dynamics component of the PolicyCLOUD project. We refer to this component as Politika. Currently, Politika runs both as a stand-alone web application on the cloud and as an external tool integrated with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD via a REST API.

2.1.5.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES SINCE D4.4

Compared to the second version as described in deliverable D4.4 [\[6\]](#) a REST API has been implemented in Politika that allows its use as an external tool integrated with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform.

2.1.5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF SIMULATION MODELS FOR POLICY ALTERNATIVES

Politika takes as input a graph corresponding to a social network and simulates its dynamics using the agent-based modelling paradigm. Politika allows the user to:

- specify, edit, or delete a simulation
- browse the specifications of simulations stored in the system
- execute simulations
- upload/download data to/from a simulation
- examine raw simulation results
- compute and visualize simulation analytics

Politika's output is the social network that results after the simulation of the dynamics of its input, and it is represented as a graph.

The Social Dynamics component uses a special-purpose language for specifying modelling individual, connection and policy attributes and dynamics. In particular, the user specifies modelling attributes as keyword/value strings. For example:

```
incubation_period: 5, infection_period: 10, immunity_period: 10, cur_icu_units: 0
```

represent the policy parameters for a containment policy in an epidemiological context. Strings ending in `:` are keyword names for parameters, while the rest are the parameter values.

Individual, connection and policy dynamics as specified as IF..DO rules. For example:

```
IF this.cur_icu_units > 0 AND this.cur_infection_death_prob >
this.baseline_infection_death_prob
DO
  this.cur_infection_death_prob:
    max(this.cur_infection_death_prob - 0.1*this.cur_infection_death_prob,
      this.baseline_infection_death_prob)
```

represents a policy dynamic rule that decreases the current infection death probability if it is above the baseline probability, provided there are icu units available.

In particular, the IF part describes a sequence of logical conditions (and, or, not) that need to be satisfied for the rule to fire, while the DO part describes new assignments for the attributes of the entity (individual, connection or policy) executing the rule. Multiple statements in the DO part are separated with the `;` marker, while different rules are separated with the `~` marker. In the case of individual attributes, the keyword `this` refers to the current individual executing the rule. The current value of such an attribute is accessed using the period (.) followed by the attribute name. For example, `this.name` refers to the name attribute of the individual executing this rule. The assignment operator is `:`; therefore the statement:

```
this.name: "Nick"
```

assigns a new value for the attribute `name` of the current individual.

In the case of connections, the keyword `edge` refers to the connection executing the current rule, the keyword `this` refers to the individual from which the connection originates while the keyword `distal` refers to the individual that is the target of the connection.

This special-purpose language has a set of built-in functions that can help the modeler in developing her social simulation. The specifications for these functions along with the rest of the Politika API are described in the reference manual for Politika at: <http://epinoetic.org/Politika/doc/api-reference.html>

2.1.5.3 THE STRUCTURE OF POLICY MODELS

Each policy model is represented as a tree structure in JSON format. For example, Figure 17 provides a screenshot of a policy model for radicalization control stored in the system. As the figure indicates, each Policy contains a list of Goals. Each Goal contains a list of Alternatives. Each Alternative contains a list of Steps that refer to simulation models stored in the system.

2.1.5.4 DESCRIPTION OF THE REST API

A REST API has been implemented that allows Politika to act as an external tool integrated with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform. To this effect, a new version of the Politika server runs at port number 5000 and accepts requests from PolicyCLOUD. The specific Politika server is a stripped-down version of the one described in deliverable D4.4 [6] as it includes a minimal number of GUI components, thus having a small footprint. It also shares the same Postgres database with the original one making it consistent with it. The server is extended with new routes that serve requests from the PolicyCLOUD PDT. Currently these requests concern the simulation of various alternatives for specific policy models stored in Politika and the reception of their results in a form compatible with a selected chart from the ones available in the PolicyCLOUD visualisation tool. Each one of these alternatives is defined with specific values for some of the policy parameters while the values of the rest of the policy parameters are taken from a list of base case values for them that is also supplied in each request. More specifically, each request consists of two string variables: Base_Case and Alternatives. The Base_case variable contains the names and values for all policy parameters in the case where no policy alternative is applied. For example:

```
"max_price: 30, price_A: 13, price_B: 11, avg_price: 15, quality_A: 0.87,
quality_B: 0.89, avg_quality: 0.85, max_income: 50000, ad_intensity_A: 0.2,
ad_intensity_B: 0.2, avg_purchase_motivation_A: 0, avg_purchase_motivation_B: 0,
purchase_motivation_ratio: 0, wine_price_ratio: -1, ad_intensity_ratio: -1, x: 0,
y: 0, z: 0"
```

describes the values of the policy parameters in the base case of an AgriFood pilot where the popularity of two competing wines A and B is estimated under different scenarios for price and advertising effort for each one.

The Alternatives variable describes alternative values for subsets of the parameters of the base case separated by the delimiter '|'. For example:

```
"price_A: 13, ad_intensity_ratio_A: 0.2 | price_A: 9, ad_intensity_A: 0.2 |
price_B: 10, ad_intensity_A: 0.4, ad_intensity_B: 0.8"
```

describes three policy alternatives for the same AgriFood pilot as before.

Once Politika receives such a request, it automatically executes all the simulations involved and sends back the results as a JSON map that can be passed on to the PolicyCLOUD visualiser as in:

```
{
  "description": "Find pricing and ad intensity ratios for an Aragon wine vs a
competitor that can provide higher purchase motivation for the Aragon wine than
its competitor. Assume that purchase motivation depends on price, quality ad
intensity and social influence. ",
  "events": [
    {
      "x": 13,
      "y": 1,
      "z": 0.9273400599850862
    },
    {

```



```
    "x": 9,
    "y": 1,
    "z": 1.0193530816097987
  },
  {
    "x": 13,
    "y": 0.5,
    "z": 0.7072078050911309
  }
],
"name": "Multi-factor Pricing Discovery for Aragon vs Competitor Wine in
PolicyCLOUD: Ignacio Marin vs Gran Sangre de Toro",
"units": {
  "ad_intensity_A": "1",
  "ad_intensity_B": "1",
  "ad_intensity_ratio": "1",
  "avg_price": "Euros",
  "avg_purchase_motivation_A": "1",
  "avg_purchase_motivation_B": "1",
  "avg_quality": "1",
  "max_income": "Euros",
  "max_price": "Euros",
  "price_A": "Euros",
  "price_B": "Euros",
  "purchase_motivation_ratio": "1",
  "quality_A": "1",
  "quality_B": "1",
  "wine_price_ratio": "1",
  "x": "1",
  "x_axes": "ARAGON wine price (in Euros)",
  "y": "1",
  "y_axes": "Ad intensity ratio between wines (ARAGON vs competitor)",
  "z": "1",
  "z_axes": "Purchase motivation ratio between wines (ARAGON vs competitor)"
},
"x_axes": "ARAGON wine price (in Euros)",
"y_axes": "Ad intensity ratio between wines (ARAGON vs competitor)",
"z_axes": "Purchase motivation ratio between wines (ARAGON vs competitor)"
}
```

The REST API we described provides a general method to interact with Politika as an external tool through the PolicyCLOUD platform. It is currently used to support two pilots in the PolicyCLOUD project relating to the Agri-Food and the Radicalization use cases.

Radicalization Control

[\[Clone\]](#) [\[Edit\]](#) [\[Delete\]](#)

- **Description:** Explores alternatives for curtailing radicals influence in a social group
- **Goals:** `{0 => {criteria: {adequacy: "radicals.avg < sympathizers.avg and sympathizers.avg < conformists.avg"}, description: "Restrict Radicals Influence", goal: 0, objectives: {0 => {description: "Maintain Status Quo", goal: 0, objective: 0, policy: 1, repetitions: 4, results: {1 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.42, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.56, sympathizers: 0.02}", 2 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.44, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.56, sympathizers: 0.0}", 3 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.46, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.54, sympathizers: 0.0}", 4 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.44, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.54, sympathizers: 0.02}"}, statistics: {conformism_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, conformists: {avg: 0.44, max: 0.46, min: 0.42}, friendship_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, radicalization_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, radicals: {avg: 0.55, max: 0.56, min: 0.54}, sympathizers: {avg: 0.01, max: 0.02, min: 0.0}}, steps: {0 => {description: "Base case with No Policy", goal: 0, objective: 0, policy: "1", results: "[]", simulation: {id: 1, new_dataset?: true}, step: 0, type: "step"}}, type: "objective"}, 1 => {description: "Restrict radicals", goal: 0, objective: 1, policy: 1, repetitions: 4, results: {1 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.54, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.44, restricted: 0.08, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.02}", 2 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.64, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.36, restricted: 0.08, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.0}", 3 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.54, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.4, restricted: 0.26, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.06}", 4 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.58, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.42, restricted: 0.22, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.0}"}, statistics: {conformism_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, conformists: {avg: 0.5750000000000001, max: 0.64, min: 0.54}, friendship_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, radicalization_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, radicals: {avg: 0.405, max: 0.44, min: 0.36}, restricted: {avg: 0.16, max: 0.26, min: 0.08}, restriction_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, sympathizers: {avg: 0.02, max: 0.06, min: 0.0}}, steps: {0 => {description: "Apply restriction policy to radicals", goal: 0, objective: 1, policy: "1", results: "[]", simulation: {id: 3, new_dataset?: true}, step: 0, type: "step"}}, type: "objective"}}, policy: 1, population_gen: "max_edges: 2, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution: :homogeneous", results: {adequacy: {0 => false, 1 => false}}, type: "goal"}}`
- **Distribution:** Public
- **Contact:** a@a.com

FIGURE 17 - SCREENSHOT OF A STORED POLICY MODEL IN POLITIKA

2.1.6 Analytical Proxy

The analytical proxy is an entirely new component developed during the third phase of the project and therefore was not included in D4.4 [6]. Its purpose is to allow the integration of the overall PolicyCLOUD platform with external analytical frameworks or tools which is very important when the capabilities of these external frameworks are not provided by the PolicyCLOUD platform. This is the case of the Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics described in the previous subsection which was the trigger for the analytical proxy.

The Analytical Proxy component acts as the intermediate function between the DAA layer and the external frameworks. It has been validated with the Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics scenario, but it has been designed in a generic way to permit integration of many other frameworks. It is provided as a built-in function of the DAA layer, which can be retrieved from the PDT layer that acts as the front-end of the external framework for the data scientist or policymaker. The data scientists or policymakers used to select analytical functions provided by the overall PolicyCLOUD solution to perform their analysis on a given set of datasets. With the introduction of the analytical proxy, they can now interact with external frameworks the same way they used to do with the built-in functions of PolicyCLOUD. From the user experience perspective, input parameters required by the external frameworks are defined at the PDT layer and then the job is submitted for execution, as described in D5.7 [4]. Upon invocation, the DAA layer deploys and executes the analytical proxy that receives the input parameters, and then interacts with the external frameworks via a REST API. This is the reason that drove the extension of the Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics to provide such an API so that it can be invoked by the PolicyCLOUD platform via the analytical proxy. The analytical proxy interacts uniformly with any external framework as it exchanges messages in a generic manner. After the external framework sends the results of the requested action (such as a simulation), the Analytical Proxy stores these results into the PDT backend so that end users can retrieve and visualise them through the PDT.

The analytical proxy has been developed in a generic manner so that it can be used for all the external frameworks. However, each framework will interact with a specifically configured instance of the analytical proxy. Each such instance will connect to the URL of the entry end point of the specific framework and forward the specific input parameters. Examples of such configuration will be given in the corresponding subsection of chapter 3.

2.1.7 Operational Data Repository

An integral part of the central data repository of PolicyCLOUD is the operational datastore provided by LXS. It is a relational database that provides support both for SQL and NoSQL executions, ensuring transactional semantics and ACID properties under very high rated data ingestion workload, due to its scalable transactional processing mechanism and the provision of an additional interface that can store data directly to its storage, bypassing the introduced footprint added by the relational query engine of the data store. As a result, it can provide support both for static data ingestion via a batch process and for ingestion of streaming data. Its functionality and features have been documented in the D4.5 [3] deliverable in section 5.3. In the scope of WP4, it has been integrated on one hand with the mechanisms developed in the scope of the DAA API Gateway, as the final component in the data ingestion pipeline

deployed by the latter will be the persistent storage of the data items into the operational datastore. Additionally, it has been integrated with those of the components developed under the scope of WP4, as analytical tools, that have the need to consume data from the persistent medium which is, at first phase, the operational datastore.

During the last phase of the project, the operational data repository has been enhanced to include the Seamless Analytical Framework, which allows to transparently access and retrieve data from a dataset that has been split between two different datastores: the operational data repository and a data warehouse. The reason for splitting datasets into different datastores is that data with high volume, being ingested with high velocity, eventually can be considered as cold and are of low value for daily operations. However, they are of high value for analytical processing, and due to their high volume, it is better to be migrated to a data warehouse, which has been properly designed to deal with big data. The issue here is that this data migration takes a lot of time (i.e., hours or even days) so data AI analytics are using outdated data. With the Seamless Analytical Framework, we can have both data (operational and obsolete data used for analytics) into separate datastores, and have a unique point of access that allows the data user to submit his or her queries in a standardised manner and let this enhancement provided during this last phase of the project to perform the query execution plan on both datastores, merge the intermediate results and return the information transparently to the data user. This mechanism is now incorporated in the overall solution provided by the operational data repository.

2.2 Interfaces

This section provides the description and details of the component interfaces.

2.2.1 DAA API Gateway

Following are the DAA API Gateway API. The API can be invoked with a command line or Rest interface.

2.2.1.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: DAA API GATEWAY

Notable changes include use cases API examples, Image based Analytic function registration (to support large analytic function implementations), addition of legal aspects in datasource and analytic functions registration and centralized logging mechanism. Initial DAA API included future fields which were not used in SW1 use cases integration and are now integrated in SW2.

2.2.1.2 ANALYTIC FUNCTION REGISTRATION

Register the analytic function as an action in OpenWhisk.

Parameters:

1. name: function name
2. kind: blackbox for image based functions, java:8/python:3 for java 8/ python 3 small footprint functions
3. filename: jar filename containing the function code
4. main: specify the function main class

5. image: this parameter must be specified if the “kind” is “blackbox”. In this case it should include the image name residing in the container registry service function parameters: function parameters (Json)
6. type: analytic / analytic-ingest
7. category: Data-Cleaning / Data-Interoperability / Situational-Knowledge / Opinion-Mining / Social-Dynamic
8. description: function description and usage
9. Expected input data schema/format
10. graph: graph format supported by PDT
11. policy: policy domain supported by PDT
12. purpose: for data access enforcement
13. biasDoc - this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input bias management documentation, providing information on the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases inherent to the functioning of the Analytics Ingest Function. It could also permit / oblige Analytic Owners to upload or indicate one or more unit test datasets on which the Analytics Ingest Function can be applied, so as to demonstrate that resulting bias measurements do not exceed a given maximum (in other words, that the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases are functioning effectively, as intended);
14. tradeoffsDoc - this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input documentation on the management of trade-offs, providing information on the relevant trade-offs encountered, decisions made concerning the balancing of competing requirements (e.g., result precision versus fairness) and measures taken to implement and document those decisions.

Return: success / failure

Spec: Register the function with all associated metadata (provided in the parameters) in OpenWhisk.

Each ingest function is expected to read the incoming data from the request’s message parameter (JSON string), and to return the transformed message as a json string.

The result JSON string might be the input of the next ingest function, or the transformation result written to PolicyCloud’s backend.

Return indicates whether analytic function successfully created as an action in OpenWhisk

Implementation details:

Analytic functions are developed by Analytic owners and can be implemented either in python or in java or node.js. and should follow OpenWhisk action implementation guidelines.

DAA uses a common GitLab structure for functions’ code registry and a common container registry for functions’ docker images with all required dependencies.

Files and images are automatically pulled from the PolicyCLOUD GitLab service during function registration to create the serverless function.

Function name should be unique.

Filename parameter specifies the filename containing the function code written under OpenWhisk conventions⁷ placed in the packaged-functions directory under the PolicyCLOUD project GitLab repository.

Main parameter specifies the main function in the above function code specified by the filename parameter.

In SW2 several types are supported: java:8, python:4 and blackbox.

java:8 type:

Use cases implementing functions in DAA should follow the guidelines to generate the jar:

- java version 8 is supported
- All dependencies should be packaged in the jar, and the jar total size should be under 48MB
- jar file should be uploaded to the PolicyCloud GitHub repository packaged-functions folder:
- maven has to be installed
- If the analytic function has external dependencies, they should be specified in pom.xml
- Sample functions jar called ReferenceFunctions.jar can be found in the project GitLab as a reference implementation for jar containing external dependencies
- Run maven clean and package to create the jar file (mvn package -Dmaven.test.skip=true)

python:3 type:

- python3 is supported
- All dependencies should be packaged in the zip, and the zip total size should be under 48MB
- zip file should be uploaded to the PolicyCloud github repository packaged-functions folder
- see <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk/blob/master/docs/actions-python.md>
- There should be a file named `__main__.py`, returning json
- Python code should be packaged into Openwhisk action
- Sample implementation file can be found in the project GitLab as a reference implementation/daa/src/main/python/ibm.functions/sample1

blackbox type:

- For functions exceeding size > 48MB use blackbox type and provide a docker file with all dependencies as well as packaged analytic code.
- Docker images should be uploaded to the project's container registry, and packaged code to the dedicated GitLab repo folder.

Python analytic example:

All dependencies should be specified in requirements.txt
Create Dockerfile

⁷ <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk/blob/master/docs/actions-java.md>

```
FROM openwhisk/actionloop-python-v3.7
```

```
COPY requirements.txt requirements.txt
```

```
RUN pip install --upgrade pip setuptools six && pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
```

```
docker build -t <IMAGE_NAME> .
```

Package analytic code: zip all files + `__main.py__`

Purpose and access policies are out of scope for SW2

Rest interface: PUT /analytic-function

The following command is an example for the registration of a cleaning **ingest** function:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
  "name": "clean",
  "kind": "blackbox",
  "image": "registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr:5050/oshrit/daa/cleanfunction:latest",
  "filename": "action.zip",
  "main": "LoadData",
  "function_parameters": "{}",
  "type": "analytic-ingest",
  "category": "cleaning",
  "description": "cleaning and interoperability",
  "biasDoc": "",
  "tradeoffsDoc": ""
}'
```

an example of an **analytic function** registration for a SentimentAggregator:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
  {
    "name": "SentimentAggregator",
    "kind": "blackbox",
    "filename": "sentimentAggregatorLXCFunction_docker.zip",
    "image": "registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr:5050/oshrit/daa/sentiment_nifi_ow",
    "function_parameters": "[
      {
        "unit": null,
        "valueType": "DATETIME",
        "name": "start_date",
        "description": "the date to start retrieving sentiments",
        "inputType": "VARIABLE",
        "id": "a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"],
        "valueConstraints": [],
        "required": true
      }
    ]
  }
}'
```



```

        "unit":null,
        "valueType":"DATETIME",
        "name":"end_date",
        "description":"the date to end retrieving sentiments",
        "inputType":"VARIABLE",
        "id":"03d31711-2614-491d-90b4-ac055fdaad3a",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"], "valueConstraints":[],
        "required":true},
    {
        "unit":null,
        "valueType":"STRING",
        "name":"per",
        "description":"the periodicity",
        "inputType":"VARIABLE",
        "id":"13d8b18f-0671-4081-ac1b-842777540b66",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
        "required":true,
        "valueConstraints":[
        { "constraintType":"VALUESALLOWED",
          "value":["second", "minute", "hour", "day"]}
        ]
    }
  ],
  ],
  "graph":["TIME_SERIES", "GAUGE"],
  "policydomain":["AGRIFOOD"],
  "type":"analytic-analysis",
  "category":"Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis",
  "description":"Aggregation of tweets based on the sentiment analysis performed
for a given period of time",
  "biasDoc":"This string expresses the bias documentation",
  "tradeoffsDoc":"This string expresses the tradeoffs documentation"
}'

```

The following example is for the registration of an heatmap analytic function:

curl -k -X PUT 90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type:

```

application/json' -d '{
  "name": "HeatMap",
  "kind": "java:8",
  "filename": "heatMap-0.0.1-SNAPSHOT.jar",
  "main": "atos.ari.data.policyCloud.heatMap.HeatMap ",
  "function_parameters": "[
    [{\"name\": \"iyear\", \"unit\": \"unit\", \"description\":
    \"param_description\", \"valueType\": \"STRING\", \"valueConstraints\":
    [{\"constraintType\": \"DEFAULT\", \"evaluationTypesAllowed\":
    [\"EQUAL\", \"GREATER\", \"GREATER_OR_EQUAL\", \"LESS\", \"LESS_OR_EQUAL\"], \"value\":
    : \"default value\"}], \"inputType\": \"VARIABLE\", \"required\":
    \"True\", \"value\": {\"type\": \"EQUAL\", \"value\": \"2004\"}}, {\"name\":
    \"region\", \"unit\": \"unit\", \"description\":
    \"param_description\", \"valueType\": \"STRING\", \"valueConstraints\":
    [{\"constraintType\": \"DEFAULT\", \"value\": \"default
    value\"}], \"evaluationTypesAllowed\":
    [\"EQUAL\", \"GREATER\", \"GREATER_OR_EQUAL\", \"LESS\", \"LESS_OR_EQUAL\"], \"inputTy

```

```
pe\": \"VARIABLE\", \"required\": true, \"value\": {\"type\": \"IN\", \"values\":  
[\"8\", \"1\"]}}}],  
\"graph\": [\"HEATMAP_POI\"],  
\"policydomain\": [\"SECURITY\"],  
\"type\": \"analytic-analysis\",  
\"category\": \"Situational-Knowledge\",  
\"description\": \"exploratory analysis in the form of data aggregations exhibiting  
the incidence of certain events\",  
\"biasDoc\": \"This string expresses the bias documentation\",  
\"tradeoffsDoc\": \"This string expresses the tradeoffs documentation\"  
}'
```

2.2.1.3 DATA SOURCE REGISTRATION

Import a data source into the database by applying ingest functions on it.

Parameters:

1. Name
2. Type (Streaming / Ingest-now / Existing)
3. Description
4. Source specification (streaming details, source data location, source URL, access method, credentials etc.)
5. Schema / metadata
6. Permissions – by whom (public / specified user list) and for what purpose the data can be used for (Analytics Functions which are to be applied to a Data Source should have been registered for purposes which are identical or compatible with the purposes identified for that Data Source)
7. Analytics Ingest Function + parameters if applicable
8. biasDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owner to input bias management documentation, providing information on the bias detection methods applied to the Data Source, the specific biases identified, and the specific measures taken to address any such biases.
9. GDPRDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input privacy / data protection management documentation which, in particular, should indicate whether any personal data is included within the Data Source and, if so, the measures taken to ensure that the Data Source can be ingested onto the platform in compliance with the applicable data protection and regulatory framework related to the processing of personal data, as defined by the GDPR and other applicable data protection laws (e.g., to ensure compliance with the principles of lawfulness, transparency and purpose limitation under the GDPR, considering the purposes for which the personal data within the Data Source were originally collected and the purposes for which those personal data will be further processed via the platform).
10. authDoc – this parameter, permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input documentation to demonstrate that the

registration of the Data Source has been authorised by relevant rightsholders (or that such authorisation is not required under applicable laws).

Return: success / fail

Spec:

1. Data source name should be unique.
2. Create the functions chain (in this prototype we demonstrate only a single function) involving Kafka topics and OpenWhisk triggers and rules, from the Kafka input topic (written into by the Cloud Gateway) to the resulting table in the DB. Create DB table.
In SW2: Creates input (T1) and output (R1) topics in Kafka, creates an action sequence with the ingest function and Kafka producer
3. For the “Ingest-now” and “Streaming” data source types, invokes the Cloud Gateway task which retrieves the data source content and place it in T1 topic
4. Register the data source with its metadata

Implementation details:

1. Supported types in SW3: Ingest-now, existing and streaming
2. T1 and R1 topic names are derived from the data source name.
3. Except for the “existing” data source type, the Cloud Gateway task is supplied with the url, Access parameters, Schema, T1 topic, and Type. It is responsible on reading the data accordingly and placing it in T1 topic
 - On Ingest-now – a simple chunks loop to place the content as messages in T1 topic
 - On Streaming – a periodic thread to place incoming streams as messages in T1 topicOpenWhisk triggers and rules created subscribe to T1 topic. Once a message was placed in the topic, the ingest-function given is invoked and the resulting new dataset is placed in R1, which in turn is written to the database.
4. The name of the data source in the DAA and the name of the data source backed table is the data source given name (Name parameter).
5. Cloud Gateway component is called to pull the dataset from the given URL

The existing data source type has been implemented in a very similar manner to the “Ingest-now” type, except that the source URL points to the location of the dataset within the LXS DataBase.

Rest interface: PUT /datasource

The following example is for the registration of a streaming datasource, with sentiment ingest function:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/datasource -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
  "ingest_functions": ["sentiment", "Leanxcale-sentiment"],
  "name": "tweet-carinena",
  "keyword": "carinena",
  "type": "stream",
  "description": "Carinena tweets",
```

```

    "access": {"type": "kafka"},
    "schema": {"name": "statuses"},
    "permissions": "UNKNOWN_PERMISSIONS",
    "url": https://api.twitter.com/1.1/search/tweets,
    "biasDoc": "This string expresses the bias documentation",
    "gdprDoc": "This string expresses the GDPR documentation",
    "authDoc": "This string expresses the authorizations documentation"
  }'

```

2.2.1.4 LIST REGISTERED FUNCTIONS

Display a detailed list of registered functions

Parameters:

1. Type: analytic / analytic-ingest

Return: List of all registered functions (analytic or analytic-ingest), each with its metadata

Rest interface: GET /analytic-function?type=

Get detailed list of all the resisted functions

```
curl -X GET "https://$URL/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function.http?type=analytic-analysis"
```

result example:

```

[
  {
    "name": "HeatMap",
    "parameters": [
      {
        {
          "key": "description",
          "value": "exploratory analysis in the form of data aggregations exhibiting the
incidence of certain events"
        },
        "key": "function_parameters",
        "value": [
          {
            "description": "param_description",
            "inputType": "VARIABLE",
            "name": "iyear",
            "required": "True",
            "unit": "unit",
            "value": {
              "type": "EQUAL",
              "value": "2004"
            }
          },
          "valueConstraints": [
            {
              "constraintType": "DEFAULT",
              "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
                "EQUAL",
                "GREATER",

```



```

        "GREATER_OR_EQUAL",
        "LESS",
        "LESS_OR_EQUAL"
    ],
    "value": "default value"
  }
]
"valueType": "STRING"
},
...},
{
  "name": "SentimentAggregator",
  "parameters": [
    {
      "key": "description",
      "value": "Aggregation of tweets based on the sentiment analysis performed for a
given period of time"
    },
    {
      "key": "function_parameters",
      "value": [
        {
          "description": "the date to start retrieving sentiments",
          "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
            "EQUAL"
          ],
          "id": "a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc",
          "inputType": "VARIABLE",
          "name": "start_date",
          "required": true,
          "unit": null,
          "valueConstraints": [],
          "valueType": "DATETIME"
        },
        ...
      ]
    }
  ]
}
}

```

2.2.1.5 LIST REGISTERED DATA SOURCES

Parameters: None

Return: List of all registered data sources, each with its metadata (including the actual DBTable)

Rest interface: GET /datasource

Get detailed list of all the resisted functions

`curl -k -X GET https://$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/datasource`

result example:

```
[
  {
    "name": "gtd",
```



```
"parameters": [  
  {  
    "key": "description",  
    "value": "Terrorist incidents"  
  },  
  {  
    "key": "type",  
    "value": "ingest"  
  },  
  ...  
]  
  
{  
  "name": "sentiments",  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "key": "description",  
      "value": "Carinena tweets"  
    },  
    {  
      "key": "type",  
      "value": "stream"  
    },  
    ...  
  ]  
}
```

2.2.1.6 APPLY FUNCTION

Invoke the requested analytics on the requested data source

Parameters:

1. UserCredentials: (TBD where is the enforcement point)
2. Function: Analytic function name
3. Parameters: for the function (json)
4. Data-source: data source name

Return: jobId/json result

Spec:

1. Invoke the OpenWhisk function (with the Parameters and data source (db table))
2. Return the OpenWhisk jobId if asynchronous. The function result in json for synchronous

Implementation details:

Job id is a wrapper for OpenWhisk activation id

Rest interface: POST / analytic-function

The following is for an Heatmap invocation on gtd datasource:

```
curl -k -X POST https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
```



```
"function": "HeatMap",
"datasource": "gtd",
"parameters":
{
  "datasource": "GTD",
  "arguments": {
    "parameters": [
      {
        "unit": "iyear",
        "valueType": "STRING",
        "name": "iyear",
        "description": "theYearsRange",
        "inputType": "VARIABLE",
        "id": "ee80842a-6fa2-42ef-bd97-6d98629555ff",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["RANGE"],
        "valueConstraints": [],
        "value": {
          "valueMax": 2004,
          "valueMin": 2004,
          "type": "RANGE"
        }
      },
      {
        "unit": "region",
        "valueType": "STRING",
        "name": "region",
        "description": "alistofregions",
        "inputType": "VARIABLE",
        "id": "31303d88-281c-49bf-9703-2097d9745df2",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["IN"],
        "valueConstraints": [],
        "value": {
          "values": ["1", "8"],
          "type": "IN"
        }
      },
      {
        "unit": null,
        "valueType": "FLOAT",
        "name": "jobid",
        "description": "theidofthenewlycreatedjob",
        "inputType": "SYSTEM",
        "id": "a17e21ac-dad2-4fba-bb39-8f72b4c0a41c",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"],
        "valueConstraints": [],
        "value": {
          "type": "EQUAL",
          "value": 1
        }
      },
      {
        "unit": null,
        "valueType": "STRING",
        "name": "graph",
        "description": "thetargetoutputvisualizationgraph",
        "inputType": "SYSTEM",
        "id": "5bbb0b0a-b740-44cf-beae-e4ac2ff52a54",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"],

```

```

    "valueConstraints": [],
    "value": {
      "type": "EQUAL",
      "value": "HEATMAP_POI"
    },
    "required": null
  }
]
}
}'

```

Example of Sentiment aggregator invocation of sentiments datasource:

```

curl -k -X POST https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-
function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '
{
  "datasource": "tweet-carinena",
  "function": "SentimentAggregator",
  "parameters": {
    "datasource": "tweet-carinena",
    "arguments": {
      "dataBase": {
        "urlDB": "jdbc:Leanxcale://90.147.170.166:1529/SARGA; user=APP",
        "user": "APP",
        "table": "SENTIMENTS"
      },
      "parameters": [
        {
          "unit": null,
          "valueType": "DATETIME",
          "name": "start_date",
          "description": "the date to start retrieving sentiments",
          "inputType": "VARIABLE",
          "id": "a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc",
          "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
            "EQUAL"
          ],
          "valueConstraints": [],
          "value": {
            "type": "EQUAL",
            "value": "2021-03-10 11:10:21"
          },
          "required": true
        },
        {
          "unit": null,
          "valueType": "DATETIME",
          "name": "end_date",
          "description": "the date to end retrieving sentiments",
          "inputType": "VARIABLE",
          "id": "03d31711-2614-491d-90b4-ac055fdaad3a",
          "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
            "EQUAL"
          ],
          "valueConstraints": [],
          "value": {

```



```
        "type": "EQUAL",
        "value": "2021-03-11 00:10:21"
    },
    "required": true
},
{
    "unit": null,
    "valueType": "STRING",
    "name": "per",
    "description": "the periodicity",
    "inputType": "VARIABLE",
    "id": "13d8b18f-0671-4081-ac1b-842777540b66",
    "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
        "EQUAL"
    ],
    "valueConstraints": [
        {
            "constraintType": "VALUESALLOWED",
            "value": [
                "second",
                "minute",
                "hour",
                "day"
            ]
        }
    ],
    "value": {
        "type": "EQUAL",
        "value": "hour"
    },
    "required": true
},
{
    "unit": null,
    "valueType": "FLOAT",
    "name": "jobid",
    "description": "the id of the newly created job",
    "inputType": "SYSTEM",
    "id": "8ef9f6af-ee06-42d8-8a62-2dc00655a7f5",
    "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
        "EQUAL"
    ],
    "valueConstraints": [],
    "value": {
        "type": "EQUAL",
        "value": 5
    },
    "required": true
},
{
    "unit": null,
    "valueType": "STRING",
    "name": "graph",
    "description": "the target output visualization graph",
    "inputType": "SYSTEM",
    "id": "ad852988-7b9f-4dc2-b676-9d2e4d5a5646",
    "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
```

```

    "EQUAL"
  ],
  "valueConstraints": [],
  "value": {
    "type": "EQUAL",
    "value": "GAUGE"
  },
  "required": true
},
{
  "unit": null,
  "valueType": "STRING",
  "name": "pdt_results",
  "description": "the url of the service to send the results",
  "inputType": "SYSTEM",
  "id": "0030259d-259a-4963-b132-46e03621dfc7",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
    "EQUAL"
  ],
  "valueConstraints": [],
  "value": {
    "type": "EQUAL",
    "value": "http://90.147.102.215:54735/pdt/jobs"
  },
  "required": true
}
]
}
}

```

2.2.1.7 GET JOB STATUS

Return the job result

Parameters:

1. jobID: id of the job

Return: Working / Completed / Failed, function json result

Spec:

1. Used for invoking asynchronous functions on data source
2. Return the job status, if completed return the function json result in the body

Implementation details:

In SW2 when the job is completed – returns the result of the invocation of the function on the data source (json) in the body. error - if job id is not found or job is not completed.

Job id is a wrapper for OpenWhisk activation id

Rest interface: GET /analytic-function?job_id=

```
curl -k -X GET https://\$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function?job\_id=123
```

2.2.2 Centralized Logging

2.2.2.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: CENTRALIZED LOGGING

This service was introduced in D4.4 [6] and was not further modified.

2.2.2.2 DETAILS OF THE LOGGING SERVICE

Appends an additional entry in the centralized log file(s).

Parameters:

1. project: project name, e.g., PolicyCloud
2. wp: work package name, e.g. daa
3. action: action name log is sent from
4. type: action type log is sent from
5. name: name of the analytic function/dataset
6. user: username if applicable
7. message: log message
8. level: log severity level

Return: Log appended

Implementation details:

The logging service is accessible to all PolicyCLOUD WPs using an HTTP API, and forms a centralized, project-wide infrastructure component. Each logging event is stored in a persistent filesystem enabled by NFS and ensures resiliency to pod failures and restarts.

This service appends an additional entry in the centralized log file(s). The list of fields logged may be modified to fit the message which is created. It is recommended to include the following fields: project, wp, action, type, name, user, message and level for all log messages to form standard structure.

Rest interface: PUT /policycloud/daa

Example of PolicyCLOUD logging event:

```
curl -H "content-type: application/json" -XPUT 'http://90.147.75.129:8088/policycloud/daa' -d '{
  "project": "policycloud",
  "wp" : "daa",
  "action": "register",
  "type": "stream",
  "name": "ds1",
  "user" : "myUserName",
  "message" : "Registering new datasource",
```

```
"level": "info"  
}'
```

2.2.3 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.2.3.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

For this third release, both the Enhanced Interoperability and Data Cleaning components are provided and can be utilized as dedicated functions through corresponding endpoints, as well as registered functions through the serverless platform of the PolicyCLOUD and more specifically the OpenWhisk component. In addition, the file, in JSON format, on which these functions will be implemented is also needed as parameter in contrary to what was documented in D4.2 and in alignment with what has been reported in D4.4 [\[6\]](#).

2.2.3.2 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The incoming HTTP requests are handled by the DataCleanerController, while the execution of the workflow is performed by the DataCleaningService. Through the provided interface the following endpoint is offered: Data Cleaning endpoint. This endpoint is responsible for handling the data cleaning workflow execution requests and providing the updated data (cleaned data) as a result of the execution. To access the Data Cleaning endpoint, the latter expects the data (either historical or streaming) for which the data cleaning workflow will be executed. The Data Cleaning endpoint is documented below:

Spec:

Initiates the data cleaning workflow and provides the estimated results.

Endpoint URL:

`http://hostname[:port]/cleaning/{file}`

HTTP method:

POST

Parameters:

file: A JSON file that contains the input data to be cleaned.

2.2.3.3 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

The incoming HTTP requests are handled by the InteroperabilityController while the execution of the workflow is performed by the InteroperabilityService. Through the provided interface the following endpoint is offered: Interoperability endpoint. This endpoint is responsible for handling the enhanced interoperability workflow as provided by the SemAI mechanism. To access the Enhanced Interoperability endpoint, the latter expects the dataset for which the SemAI mechanism will be executed in JSON format. The final exposed Enhanced Interoperability endpoint is documented below:

Spec:

Initiates the enhanced interoperability workflow and provides the estimated results.

Endpoint URL:

http://hostname[:port]/interoperability/{file}

HTTP method:

POST

Parameters:

file: A JSON file that contains the input data to be cleaned.

2.2.4 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

2.2.4.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

The changes between the second and the last prototypes can be found in "Summary of change: Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis" in 2.1.3.2.

2.2.4.2 SKA-EDA COMPONENT

2.2.4.2.1 USER INTERFACES FOR SKA-EDA

For this last release, a set of core services have been provided for exploratory data analysis

- **Frequency distribution across one category along a period.** i.e.: number of road incidents (number of observations) by "district" (variable1) for a month (initDate: and endDate). .
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /univariableFrequencyDistribution
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the period
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the period
variable1	query	string	true	Attribute of the dataset to be explored* (i.e: <i>district</i>)
payload	body		true	Json with the raw data

TABLE 1 – PARAMETERS FOR FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION SINGLE CATEGORY

*any variable belonging to the database can be included as variable1 in the service

- **Frequency distribution across several categories along a period.** I.e: number of road incidents (number of observations) per “month” (variable1) and per “category” (variable2) for a year (initDate: endDate).
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /bivariableFrequencyDistribution
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the period
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the period
variable1	query	string	true	First attribute of the dataset to be explored (in the x-axes) (i.e: <i>monthYear</i>)*
variable2	query	string	true	Second attribute of the dataset to be explored (each x-axes point) (i.e: <i>category</i>)*
head	query	integer	true	Reduce second variable to the most N repeated values (modes)
stacked	query	bool	true	Whether the bar chart can be shown stacked or not
payload	body		true	Json with the raw data

TABLE 2 – PARAMETERS FOR FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION MULTIPLE CATEGORIES

*any variable belonging to the database can be included as variables1 and variable2 in the service

- **Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories along a period.** I.e: the accumulation of the attribute “Value” (last numerical attribute in the dataset) number of claimants) across “monthYear” (variable1) and “gender” (variable2).
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /bivariateAccumulatedDistribution
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the period
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the period
variable1	query	string	true	First attribute of the dataset to be explored (in the x-axes) (i.e: <i>monthYear</i>)*
variable2	query	string	true	Second attribute of the dataset to be explored (each x-axes point) (i.e: <i>category</i>)*
payload	body		true	Json with the raw data

TABLE 3- PARAMETERS FOR SINGLE VARIABLE ACCUMULATION FOR MULTIPLE CATEGORIES

*any variable belonging to the database can be included as variable1 and variable2 in the service. The dataset must have a numerical variable over which make the accumulation

- **Geographical distribution of list of events/signals that happen in the specific values of a geographical variable along a period.** I.e.: number of road incidents (number of observations) per geographical location (per district) district (variable1). along a period.
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /univariableGeographicalDistribution
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the period
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the period
variable1	query	string	true	Located-based attribute of the dataset (i.e: district)
payload	body		true	Json with the raw data

TABLE 4 – PARAMETERS FOR EVENTS/SIGNALS GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION

*any variable belonging to the database can be included as variable1 as long as it will be a location-based variable (such as: neighbourhood, district, cities, countries....) and the dataset includes the location for the events

- **Temporal Evolution**, the changes in the value of an attribute by the passage of time for certain categories in a dataset filtered by the "name" attribute. I.e.: the fluctuation of "price" (variable) for the following categories based on the attribute "name": "Albada 2013 Viñas Viejas Garnacha (Calatayud), Grandes Vinos y Viñedos 2015 Corona de Aragón Garnacha (Cariñena), Idrias 2007 Sevil Red (Somontano), Idrias 2011 Chardonnay (Somontano)" (listEntities) for a month (intiDate: endDate:)

- Method: POST
- Route: /temporalEvolution
- Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the period
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the period
variable	query	string	true	Attribute of the entities to be monitored (for the price monitoring scenario should be always "price")
maxNumber	query	string	true	max number of entities to be monitored. Can be empty
listEntities	query	string	true	List of entities name selected by the user
payload	body		true	json with the raw data

TABLE 5 – PARAMETERS FOR TEMPORAL EVOLUTION

Some consideration regarding the parameters:

- So far, the user must know and write the exact name of the desired wines
- If the number of wines in the list exceeds maxNumber, the list will be truncated to the first maxNumber wines name
- Although the user will select the name of wines, the tool will take into account both "winery" and "name" for the accounting due to there are different wines with the same name
- The list of wines can be empty, in this case the tool will retrieve the wines with the top-maxNumber most common names in the dataset. See this list in "filterValue" element in Figure 22.

*any variable belonging to the database can be included as variable

2.2.4.2.2 INTEGRATION WITHIN POLICYCLOUD

In terms of integration with the rest of PolicyCLOUD components, the SKA-EDA services are integrated into NiFi-based pipelines which route the data from the PolicyCLOUD storage to the PDT PolicyCLOUD backend. These NiFi pipelines are wrapped into OpenWhisk-oriented Python scripts and deployed as OpenWhisk actions ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway.

2.2.4.2.3 SKA-EDA OUTPUTS EXAMPLES

The SKA-EDA analysis outputs a json file containing the categories to be depicted in a bar chart. It is a list of *categories/occurrences* objects where each of them sharing the following general metadata:

- "stacked": true if the (bar) chart is shown stacked. False by default
- "filterToUse": attribute of the dataset used for filtering the data at visualisation time
- "filterValue": values from the "filterToUse" attribute used in the filtering
- "x-axes": name of x-axes
- "y-axes": name of y-axes
- "name": name of the distributions shown
- "description": brief description of the distributions shown
- "startDate": the initial date of the period to be analysed
- "endDate": the end date of the period to be analysed. If the end date is null the analysis is performed for a concrete moment denoted by start date
- "events": the result data. This "events" element acquires different formats depending on the type of distributions:
 - Frequency distribution for one variable:
 - "events": a list of elements, where each element contains two elements:
 - key, a specific value (category) for variable 1
 - value, the occurrences of this value
 - Frequency distribution for different variables and accumulation distributions:
 - "n": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in the second variable". i.e: If 0, all the values from variable2 will be considered. If 3, just the top-3 most popular values of variable2 will be shown in the json.
 - "events": a list of elements, where each element contains N elements:
 - specific value₁ (category₁) for variable 2: the occurrences of this value
 -
 - specific value_N (category_N) for variable 2: occurrences of this value
 - category: the variable1 value

As it can be seen, the result format is general enough to host the result of different types of aggregation related to one categorical variable. It will be a matter of replacing the variable 1 to make this SKA-EDA analysis reusable for other different data sources/variables.

Below, it can be shown an example of the output of the */univariableFrequencyDistribution* service with following parameters:

- variable1: "district"
- startDate: "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000"
- endDate: "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"

```
{
  "stacked": false,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "district",
  "y-axes": "observations",
  "name": "frequency distribution across one (or several) categories",
  "description": "number of observations in Road Infrastructure per district",
```

```

"startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
"endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
"n": {
  "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in ",
  "value": 3
},
"events": [
  {
    "key": "район Банкя",
    "values": 25
  },
  {
    "key": "район Витоша",
    "values": 571
  },
  {
    "key": "район Връбница",
    "values": 139
  },
  ...
]
}

```

FIGURE 18 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE1

Below, we show an example of the output of the */bivariableFrequencyDistribution* service with following parameters:

- variable1: "monthYear"
- variable2: "type description"
- startDate: "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000"
- endDate: "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"
- stacked: "false"
- head: 0

```

{
  "stacked": True,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "monthYear",
  "y-axes": "observations",
  "name": "frequency distribution across one (or several) categories",
  "description": "number of observations in Road Infrastructure per monthYear(x-axes) and per type_description(in colours)",
  "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
  "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
  "n": {
    "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in ",
    "value": 3},
  "events": [
    {
      "Липсващи или повредени стационарни антипаркинг стълбчета": 190,
      "Неправомерно поставяне върху тротоари на оградащи елементи": 122,

```

```

"Счупени или липсващи капацитети на шахти": 81,
"category": "2020-01"},
{"Липсващи или повредени стационарни антипаркинг стълбчета": 148, "Неправомерно
поставяне върху тротоари на оградащи елементи": 98, "Счупени или липсващи капацитети на
шахти": 93, "category": "2020-02"}, ...]
}

```

FIGURE 19 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE2

Below, it can be shown an example of the output of the */bivariateAccumulatedDistribution* service with following parameters:

- variable1: "monthYear"
- variable2: "Gender Name"
- startDate: "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000"
- endDate: "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"

```

{
  "stacked": false,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "monthYear",
  "y-axes": "claimants",
  "name": "distribution of Value (number of claimants) across multiples categories",
  "description": "number of claimants in JSA And UC Claimants In Camden per
monthYear(x-axes) and per Gender Name(in colours)",
  "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
  "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
  "n": {
    "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in Gender Name",
    "value": 3
  },
  "events": [
    {"Female": 3435, "Male": 4725, "Total": 8260, "category": "2020-01"},
    {"Female": 3625, "Male": 4850, "Total": 8515, "category": "2020-02"},
    {"Female": 3645, "Male": 4885, "Total": 8690, "category": "2020-03"},
    {"Female": 6305, "Male": 8260, "Total": 14570, "category": "2020-04"},
    ...
  ]
}

```

FIGURE 20 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE3

The SKA-EDA analysis, in the case of geographical distribution, outputs a json file containing a list of events that happened in the specific values of the geographical variable. See below the json description:

- "level": administrative divisions used for centering the map of the use case area of research (i.e.: country, city, ...)
- "name": name of the administrative division used for centering the map of the use case area of research (i.e: Bulgaria, Sofia, ...)

- "location": a GeoJson object which describes the use case area of research (i.e.: the GeoJson location of the Sofia city)
- "data", a list of elements, each of them with the following fields:
 - "events", a list containing the events found in a particular value of the geographical variable (i.e: if the analysis is a geographical distribution of the variable "district", this list will contain the events that happen in each of the values of the variable "district", for example all the events that happen in "Повредена спирка" district). For each event following information is attached
 - "eventid": identifier of the event
 - "timestamp": 1582796185706,
 - "latitude": latitude where the event happens,
 - "longitude": longitude where the event happens
 - "year": year when the event happens
 - "month": month when the event happens
 - "day": day when the event happens
 - "esummary": description of the event
 - location2: a GeoJson object describing the location a specific value of the geographical variable (i.e: the GeoJson location of the "Повредена спирка" district).
 - num_events: number of events found in a particular value of the geographical variable (i.e.: the total number of events found in the "Повредена спирка" district)
 - "startDate": the init date of the period to be analysed
 - "endDate": the end date of the period to be analysed. If the end date is null the analysis is performer for a concrete moment denoted by start date

Below, an example of the output of the *UnivariableGeographicalDistribution* service with the following parameters:

- variable1: "district"
- startDate: "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000"
- endDate: "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"

```
{
  "level": "city",
  "name": "Sofia",
  "location": {"type": "Point", "coordinates": [23.329334, 42.719941]},
  "data":
  [
    {"events": [
      {"eventid": 194593,
        "timestamp": 1582796185706,
        "latitude": "42.7145446150652",
        "longitude": "23.1410249588608",
```

```
"iyear": 2020,
"imonth": 2,
"iday": 27,
"esummary": "Повредена спирка."},

{"eventid": 223511,
"timestamp": 1601374103001,
"latitude": "42.7066619684188",
"longitude": "23.1562459819193",
"iyear": 2020,
"imonth": 9,
"iday": 29,
"esummary": "Заградено пътно плат"},
...
],
"location2": {"region_txt": "район Банкя", "region": 1},
"num_events": 25, "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
"endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"},
{"events": [
{"eventid": 187286,
"timestamp": 1578047199340,
"latitude": "42.6414943744128",
"longitude": "23.2938613793457",
"iyear": 2020,
"imonth": 1,
"iday": 3,
"esummary": "Запазват се места."},
{"eventid": 187324,
"timestamp": 1578060333283,
"latitude": "42.6528811953623",
"longitude": "23.2632676652902",
"iyear": 2020,
"imonth": 1,
"iday": 3,
"esummary": "Саксии на пътя, коит"},
...
],
"location2": {"region_txt": "район Триадица", "region": 24},
"num_events": 686,
"startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
"endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"
}
],
"id": 2,
"typeOfCharts": "HEATMAP_POI"
}
```

FIGURE 21 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE

Finally, regarding the Temporal Evolution the json file output contains a list of entities with their values for "price" attribute for a specific day and for different vendors. With the following elements:

- "filterToUse": attribute of the dataset used for filtering the data at visualisation time. For this specific analytical tool will always be "name ontology".
- "filterValue": values from the "filterToUse" attribute used in the filtering
- "x-axes": name of x-axes.

- "y-axes": name of y-axes.
- "name": name of the distributions shown.
- "description": brief description of the distributions shown.
- "startDate": the initial date of the period to be analysed
- "endDate": the end date of the period to be analysed. If the end date is null the analysis is performed for a concrete moment denoted by start date.
- "data", list of entities, each of them with the following fields:
 - "events", a list containing the "price" from different vendors for a concrete entity. For each event following information is attached
 - "vendor1": price for vendor 1
 - "vendor2: price for vendor 2
 - ...
 - "category": the date
 - "name_ontology": the name of the entity
 - "winery": the winery of the entity

Below, an example of the output of the */temporalEvolution* service with the following parameters:

- start_date: "2022-05-07 15:24:21.000"
- end_date: "2022-06-14 23:23:46.000"
- variable: "price"
- maxNumber: "10"
- listEntities:[]

```
{
  "description": "temporal evolution of price per name_ontology",
  "endDate": "2022-06-14 23:23:46.000",
  "filterToUse": "name_ontology",
  "filterValue": [
    "Coto de Hayas Garnacha Centenaria",
    "Alto Moncayo",
    "Wings Golondrina Garnacha y Cariñena",
    "Monasterio de Las Viñas Old Vine Garnacha",
    "Monasterio de Las Viñas Garnacha y Tempranillo",
    "Beso de Vino Garnacha Blanca Aragocista",
    "Cruz de Piedra Blanco Macabeo - Garnacha Blanca",
    "Monte Odina Rosado Cabernet Sauvignon",
    "Viñas de Antillon Blanco",
    "Borsao Rosado Clasico"
  ],
  "name": "Temporal Evolution of price by winery_name_ontology",
  "startDate": "2022-05-07 15:24:21.000",
  "x-axes": "timestamp",
  "y-axes": "price"
  "data": [
    {
      "events": [
        {
          "category": "2022-06-09",
          "winemag": 14.19
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```
    }
  ],
  "name_ontology": "Wings Golondrina Garnacha y Cariñena",
  "winery": "Alto Cinco"
},
{
  "events": [
    {
      "category": "2022-06-09",
      "winemag": 42.58
    }
  ],
  "name_ontology": "Alto Moncayo",
  "winery": "Alto Moncayo"
},
{
  "events": [
    {
      "category": "2022-06-09",
      "winemag": 18.93
    }
  ],
  "name_ontology": "Monte Odina Rosado Cabernet Sauvignon",
  "winery": "Bodega Otto Bestué"
},... ]
}
```

FIGURE 22 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE

2.2.4.3 SKA-TSF COMPONENT

2.2.4.3.1 USER INTERFACES FOR SKA-TSF

Following is the swagger documentation for the REST API, for the fourth core services implemented in the context of time series forecasting.

Two services for training the models. These two services are subject to be used by the data science in charge of analysing the time series and training the models:

- **trainingProphet** (from file)

FIGURE 23 - SKA-TSF TRAINING PROPHET SERVICE INTERFACE

where:

- datasetName: the training dataset name
 - hyper-parameters: the user can train the Prophet model with custom parameters. If empty, Prophet will be trained with the default parameters resulting from step 2 (*Parameter estimation*) and commented in section 2.1.3.2 dealing with Predictive analysis.
 - description: a brief description of what predicts the model
- **triningSarima** (from file)

FIGURE 24 - SKA-TSF TRAINING SARIMA SERVICE INTERFACE

where:

- `datasetName`: the training dataset name
- `hyper-parameters`: the user can train Sarima model with custom parameters. If empty, Sarima will be trained with the default parameters resulting from the step 2 (*Parameter estimation*) and commented in section 2.1.3.2 dealing with Predictive analysis.
- `description`: a brief description of what predicts the model.

The two following services are the core functionality for predicting outcomes. These two services are subject to be used for the python-based predicting time series pipeline that is commented in subsection “Integration with PolicyCLOUD”.

- **predictingProphet:**

FIGURE 25 – SKA-TSF PREDICTING PROPHET SERVICE INTERFACE

where

- `datasetName`: trained model, given by the name of the training dataset. This service will predict with the most recent model trained with this training dataset name.
- `horizon`: specified time horizon, the number of future outcomes to predict (expressed in days). It's worth mentioning that the predicting process will throw reliable outcomes for the future within the next 1-3 months from the last period (in our case, last day) of the trained dataset used in the selected model.

- **predictingSarima:**

FIGURE 26 – SKA-TSF PREDICTING SARIMA SERVICE INTERFACE

where:

- datasetName: trained model, given by the name of the training dataset. This service will predict with the help of the most recent model trained with this training dataset name.
- startDate: the date to start retrieving future observations
- endDate: the date to end retrieving future observations

It's worth mentioning that the predicting process will throw reliable outcomes for the future within the next 1-3 months from the last period (in our case, last day) of the trained dataset used in the selected model.

2.2.4.3.2 INTEGRATION WITHIN POLICYCLOUD

In terms of integration with the rest of PolicyCLOUD components, the SKA-TSF predicting services are integrated into OpenWhisk-oriented Python scripts which receive a set of parameters, perform the predictions and leave the results into the PDT PolicyCLOUD backend. These Python scripts are deployed as OpenWhisk actions ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway.

2.2.4.3.3 SKA-TSF OUTPUTS EXAMPLES

Regarding the output of the two predictor services: `/predictingSarima` and `/predictingProphet`, the following json format is output-ed for both:

- "x-axes": "timestamp" (fixed)
- "y-axes": "number of incidents" (fixed)
- "name": "time series forecasting" (fixed)
- "description": brief description of the prediction including the model used to
- "startDate": the initial date of the period to be predicted
- "endDate": the end date of the period to be predicted

- “event”, a list of elements containing data points ordered in time. Whether the data point is real (taking from the historical data) or predicted (forecasted from the model) the elements can be of two different types:
 - historical elements:
 - category: the point of time
 - real: real value
 - predicted elements
 - category: the point of time
 - "lower": low limit of the confidence interval)
 - "upper": upper limit of the confidence interval,
 - "value": predicted value

The historical elements comprise from the startDate to one year ago (for predictingSarima) and from the last day of the training dataset to one year ago (for predictingProphet).

See in the figure below an example of the predicting output for */predictingSarima* with following parameters:

- start_date: 2020-05-01 00:00:28.000
- end_date: 2020-07-29 23:59:55.000

```
{ "x-axes": "timestamp",
  "y-axes": "incidents",
  "name": "time series forecasting",
  "description": "time series forecasting with seasonal arima",
  "startDate": "2020-05-01 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2020-07-29 00:00:00",
  "events": [
    {
      "real": 20,
      "category": "2019-05-02 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "real": 15,
      "category": "2019-05-03 00:00:00"
    },
    ...
    {
      "lower": -0.4979610747262022,
      "upper": 34.39709215790455,
      "value": 16.949565541589177,
      "category": "2020-07-28 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "lower": 1.1641225625493412,
      "upper": 36.08503331501336,
      "value": 18.62457793878135,
      "category": "2020-07-29 00:00:00"
    }
  ]
}
```

```
}
  ]
}
```

FIGURE 27 - SKA-EDA RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE

2.2.5 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

2.2.5.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPINION MINING & SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The previous prototype delivered by this task, reported in the 2nd prototype (D4.4), was focused on the work done in the context of Sentiment analysis. In particular, the first experiments done in the context of the entity-level sentiment analysis based on deep learning approaches (such as BERT) were reported as the second prototype of the opinion and sentiment analysis task.

For this third and last release, two final prototypes are reported:

- Final version of the Entity-level sentiment analysis tool, fully specified in D4.5
- Final version of the new Trend analysis tool, fully specified in D4.5.

2.2.5.2 USER INTERFACES

2.2.5.2.1 USER INTERFACES FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The new services provided by the sentiment analysis tool are described in the following definition:

- Aggregator
 - Method: GET
 - Route: /aggregator
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the aggregation
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the aggregation
periodicity	query	string	true	Periodicity to aggregate the data (second, minute, hour or day)
dbURL	query	string	true	URL pointing to the database endpoint containing the tweet annotations
dbUser	query	string	true	User id to connect to the database endpoint

TABLE 6 – PARAMETERS FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS AGGREGATOR

- Sentiment by aspect
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /sentimentAspect

- Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
payload	body	json	true	Json with the tweet data and the entities recognized

TABLE 7 – PARAMETERS FOR SENTIMENT BY ASPECT

2.2.5.2.2 USER INTERFACES FOR TREND ANALYSIS

The Services provided by the trend analysis tool are described in the following definition:

- Conceptualizer
 - Method: POST
 - Route: /conceptualizer
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
dbUri	query	string	true	Uri of the db to query and store data
dbUser	query	string	true	User to connect to the database
writeToDB	query	boolean	true	Flag to write or not the result of the query into the database
table	query	string	true	Which table to generate results for ("tweet", "annotation", "all")
payload	body	json	true	Tweet and entities recognized

TABLE 8 – PARAMETERS FOR TREND ANALYSIS CONCEPTUALIZER

- Tag Cloud generation
 - Method: GET
 - Route: /trendAggregationAnalysis
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDate	query	string	true	Initial date of the tweets to aggregate (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
endDate	query	string	true	End date of the tweets to aggregate (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
cloudType	query	string	true	Tag cloud type to generate: 1-3 category-based filter; 4,6 Item-based filter; 7-8 Bursty concept
dbUri	query	string	true	URi of the db to query and store data
dbUser	query	string	true	User to connect to the database

TABLE 9 – PARAMETERS FOR TAG CLOUD GENERATION

- Bursty analysis
 - Method: GET
 - Route: /burstyAnalysis
 - Parameters:

name	in	type	required	description
initDateI	query	string	true	Initial date of the tweets to aggregate in the reference time window (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
endDateI	query	string	true	End date of the tweets to aggregate in the reference time window (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
initDateII	query	string	true	Initial date of the tweets to aggregate in the compared time window (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
endDateII	query	string	true	End date of the tweets to aggregate in the compared time window (with format "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.fffZ")
maxNumber	query	string	true	Max number of results to offer
dbUri	query	string	true	URi of the db to query and store data
dbUser	query	string	true	User to connect to the database

TABLE 10 – ARGUMENTS FOR BURSTY ANALYSIS

2.2.5.3 OUTPUT EXAMPLES

2.2.5.3.1 OUTPUT EXAMPLES OF TREND-ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

Here is the description of the outputs given by the services offered by the trend analysis component in PolicyCLOUD:

- Conceptualizer

In the case of the conceptualizer service, the following information is added to the tweet json provided as input:

1. For the entities that belong to the use case model (are present in the ontology of the use case) that were explicitly identified in the text, the sentiment analysis output is added with the following data:
 - a. sentiment: the sentiment provided by the sentiment analysis analytic tool
 - b. sentiment_score: the sentiment score provided by the sentiment analysis analytic tool
 - c. explicit: this flag is set to true as those entities were identified in the original tweet text
2. Additionally, new entities are added to the output of the service. In this case, all those entities that are linked to those entities that are explicitly mentioned in the text will be added as implicit annotations (e.g., if a wine is mentioned in a tweet, that wine will be an explicit annotation while the winery and the region that produce that wine will be added as implicit annotations).

An example of output provided by this service is provided in section 5.1.1

While the output jsons of this service should be validated according to the json schema that can be found in 5.1.2

- Tag cloud generator

The tag cloud generator service output might vary depending on the cloud type requested. For instance, the output of the category-based tag cloud generator will follow the structure here shown:

- type_uri: the URI that identifies the category used as filter
- type_name: the name of the category used as filter
- events: the different number of mentions for the elements that belong the current category
 - item_uri: the URI that identifies the current item
 - numMentions: the number of mentions of the current item

An example of output for the tag cloud is given at section 5.2.1

And this json could be validated according to the json schema given at 5.2.2

- Bursty analysis

For the output format of the bursty analysis, the requirements from the visualization component of this analytical component were taken as guideline , providing their required structure in the results:

- startDate: initial date of time window I
- endDate: enddate of time window I

- startDatell: initial date of time window II
- endDatell: end date of time window II
- EventsDown: list of top elements with less mentions in time window II than in time window I
 - id & count pair
 - category: String indicating the type of table to show the results (old, new, difference, percentage)
- EventsUp: list of top elements with more mentions in time window II than in time window I
 - id & count pair
 - category: String indicating the type of table to show the results (old, new, difference, percentage)

An example of output for this service is shown at 5.3.1

2.2.5.3.2 OUTPUT EXAMPLES OF ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

The services implemented in the entity-level sentiment analysis component in policyCLOUD will offer the outputs according to the following description:

- Aggregator

The output of the aggregator will consist of:

- startDate: the start date of the time window to be analysed
- endDate: the end date of the time window to be analysed
- data: the resultant data of the aggregation
 - Filter: category of the elements that will serve as filter
 - items: the list of items that belong to the category value in “filter”
 - id: URI of the item to be used as filter
 - countries: a list of elements, each one containing info of the tweets of a country
 - id: the ID of the country
 - sentiment: Summary of the sentiment for this item in this country
 - sentiment_score: the aggregated score of the sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country
 - sentiment: the aggregated sentiment for the current item in the tweets for the current country
 - sentiment_counts: the counts of the different sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country
 - count: the overall count of the total sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country
 - historical:
 - initDate: the start date of the time window to be analysed
 - endDate: the end date of the time window to be analysed
 - periodicity: the periodicity of the temporal analysis (day, hour, etc.)
 - Aggregates
 - sentiment_score: the aggregated score of the sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country for the current periodic time window
 - sentiment: the aggregated sentiment for the current item in the tweets for the current country for the current periodic time window
 - sentiment_counts: the counts of the different sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country for the current periodic time window
 - count: the overall count of the total sentiments for the current item in the tweets for the current country for the current periodic time window

- `initDate`: the start date for the current periodic time window
- `endDate`: the end date for the current periodic time window

An example of a shortened output is given at subsection 5.4.1

This output should be validated according to the json schema given at 5.4.2

- Sentiment by aspect:

Regarding the output provided by the sentiment by aspect service, for each annotation of an entity provided in the input json, the following structure will be added:

- `sentiments`:
 - `sentiment`: the name of the sentiment identified for the current entity
 - `sentiment_weights`: the weight for the different candidate sentiments
 - `sentiment_score`: the score of the sentiment identified for the current entity
 - `review`: the model weights related to the different elements in the text to provide the sentiment chosen.

An example of an output is given at subsection 5.5.1

Providing output jsons according to the json schema detailed at subsection 0

2.2.5.4 INTEGRATION

2.2.5.4.1 INTEGRATION OF TREND-ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

The integration of the trend analysis services in Policy Cloud follows a similar approach than the document-based sentiment delivered for the first release of the sentiment analysis detailed in D4.2. Therefore, it consists of two independent processes:

- **Ingest Function**: A OpenWhisk-oriented Python script responsible for applying the conceptualizer to the tweets. It generates a set of ontology-based implicit and explicit mention to the entities found in the text. It is meant to be run in streaming mode as an ingest function. Therefore, it takes the data from input Kafka topic(s), computes the conceptualization of the detected entities (by means of the `/conceptualizer` service) and stores the results in the PolicyCLOUD Data Storage. This Python script is deployed as OpenWhisk actions ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway.
- **Aggregate Functions**: A set of OpenWhisk-oriented Python scripts in charge of performing some data aggregations based on the mentions extracted in the previous process. These aggregators take a set of input parameters, execute microservices related with the aggregation (by means of the `/trendAggregationAnalysis` and `/burstyAnalysis` services) and put the results into the PDT backend. These Python scripts are deployed as OpenWhisk actions ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway.

2.2.5.4.2 INTEGRATION OF ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

The integration of the entity-level sentiment and trend analysis services in Policy Cloud follows a similar approach than the document-based sentiment delivered for release 1 detailed in D4.2. Therefore, it consists of two independent processes:

- **Ingest Function:** A first OpenWhisk-oriented Python script is responsible for the entity-based sentiment analysis per se. It generates positive/negative/neutral tags related to the ontology-based entities found in the text. It is meant to be run in streaming mode as an ingest function. Therefore, it takes the data from input Kafka topic(s), computes the entity-level sentiment analysis (by means of the /sentimentAspect microservice) and stores the results in the PolicyCLOUD Data Storage. This Python script is deployed as OpenWhisk actions ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway.
- **Aggregate Function:** A second OpenWhisk-oriented Python script is responsible for performing some data aggregations based on the tags extracted in the previous process. The output aggregates contain a summary (number of positive/negative/neutral mentions and an average score) split with a concrete periodicity (second/minute/hour/and more) for a given period of time. This process gets the data from the PolicyCLOUD Datastore (tweets + mentions tables), performs the aggregates (by means of invoking the /aggregator microservice) and stores the results back again in the PDT Backend. It implies a set of parameters such as: datastore endpoint and other important parameters that define how to aggregate are: start date, end date and periodicity. This Python script is deployed as OpenWhisk action ready to be invoked by the DAA API Gateway

2.2.6 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

2.2.6.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: SOCIAL DYNAMICS AND BEHAVIOURAL DATA ANALYTICS

Previously the Social Dynamics module supported the development, simulation, and analysis of policy models in isolation. Now this module has been transformed into a more general framework for supporting policy design that allows the specification, simulation, and comparison of multiple policy alternatives. To this end we have developed novel, graphical user interfaces for the development and execution of meta-simulation structures that (i) describe and apply various modelling assumptions on the simulation of multiple policy alternatives, (ii) allow the specification of various criteria for comparing the simulation results of various policy alternatives, and (iii) provide 2D and 3D graph visualizations of the social network that results from each simulation cycle.

Since D4.4 [\[6\]](#) we have proceeded with the implementation of the REST API described in section 2.1.5.4 through which Politika is integrated with the rest of the PolicyCLOUD environment. This new implementation consisted of the definition of new HTTP routes through which PolicyCLOUD analytic functions can interact with specific policy models, along with an environment for dynamically creating and executing policy alternatives based on the parsing of the data received from PolicyCLOUD and for communicating the results back to the PolicyCLOUD environment in a format consistent with the selected visualization methods employed by PolicyCLOUD.

2.2.6.2 USER INTERFACES FOR SOCIAL DYNAMICS & BEHAVIOURAL DATA ANALYTICS

We describe the options available to the user for interacting with the latest version of Politika and provide relevant screenshots.

The main screen of the system lists the existing policy/simulation models in the system and allows the user to create a new policy/simulation model. Existing policies and simulations are listed either as Public meaning that their author has given editing permissions to all users or as My Policies/Simulations meaning that they have been created by the logged-in user.

The screenshot shows the user interface for 'baba' with a 'Log out' button. A light blue banner says 'Welcome back!'. Below are sections for 'Policies' and 'Simulations'. Under 'Policies', there is a 'New Policy' link and a 'My Policies' section containing one item: 'Radicalization Control - Explores alternatives for curtailing radicals influence in a social group'. Under 'Simulations', there is a 'New Simulation' link and a 'My Simulations' section containing three items: 'Restiction Policy for Radicals - Explores the consequences of restricting the interaction of radicals with the rest of the population', 'Base case for Radicalization - Explores what may happen to a social group when radicalization is left unchecked', and 'Containment Policy for Radicalization - Seek to contain radicalization by restricting the social influence of radicals'. Below that is a 'Public Simulations' section containing the same three items as 'My Simulations'.

FIGURE 28 – POLITIKA INTRO SCREEN FOR LISTING EXISTING OR CREATING POLICIES/SIMULATIONS

Clicking on New Simulation the user is presented with a form for creating a new simulation. The form contains a set of text boxes that the user needs to fill. After submitting the form, it is checked for syntactic correctness of the various fields. If all fields are correct a new simulation is created in the database, otherwise the system displays the same form as filled by the user and containing a list of messages describing the errors messages that were spotted in the user input.

Selecting any of the listed simulations the user can inspect the simulation parameters. A top menu allows him to edit these parameters, run the simulation, examine its results, delete the simulation or perform analysis of these results,

The Edit option extends the form described for the New simulation option with the additional options to:

- upload social network data from a user-supplied text file in JSON format using the Input Network field
- create synthetic data for a social network automatically by the system using the New radio button. In this case the user needs to specify the size of the social network (the number of nodes in the graph) and the Generator parameters that will be used for generating the network.

Edit Base case for Radicalization

Title

Base case for Radicalization

Description

Explores what may happen to a social group when radicalization is left unchecked

Public?

Private?

Policy related parameters

radicals: 0, sympathizers: 0, conformists: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5,
conformism_threshold: 0, friendship_threshold: 0

Individual attributes

radicalization_status: rand_float(-1, 1), x: rand_int(-200, 200), y: rand_int(-200, 200), z:
rand_int(1, 5), red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0, 255), blue: rand_int(0, 255),
alpha: 0.75, radius: 10, scale: 1

Connection attributes

contact_strength: rand_float(-1, 1), influence: 0, red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0,
255), blue: rand_int(0, 255)

Policy related dynamics

```
IF true DO this.radicals: global_count("this.radicalization_status >  
global.radicalization_threshold", population)/size; this.sympathizers:  
global_count("this.radicalization_status > global.conformism_threshold and  
this.radicalization_status > global.radicalization_threshold" population)/size;
```

Node dynamics

```
IF true DO this.radicalization_status: this.radicalization_status + sum_in(this.state,  
"edge.influence") ~ IF this.radicalization_status < -1 DO this.radicalization_status: -1  
~ IF this.radicalization_status > 1 DO this.radicalization_status: 1 ~ IF true DO this.x:  
this.x + 2 @this.radicalization_status; this.y: this.y + this.radicalization_status
```

Connection dynamics

```
IF true DO edge.influence: this.radicalization_status * edge.contact_strength
```


New network

Size

50

Generator

```
max_edges: 5, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution:  
:homogeneous
```

Use existing network

Import network

No file chosen

Cycles

10

Sampling period

1

FIGURE 29- EDITING FORM FOR A SIMULATION IN POLITIKA (UPPER AND LOWER PARTS)

The Delete option allows the user to delete a specific simulation from Politika after the user confirms this choice through a confirmation window displayed on the screen.

The Results option shows a list of nodes and their resulting attributes for each node in the social network after the simulation has finished. The details of each node are displayed in raw text form.

Scaled Node Attributes for Radicalization Demo

The horizontal axis lists all nodes. Attribute values are shown as equal-width rectangles linearly scaled from a domain of their min and max values to a height between 0 and 1 on the vertical axis. Moving the cursor on top of a rectangle, shows the value of its corresponding attribute.

FIGURE 32 - EXAMPLE ATTRIBUTE VALUES FOR EACH NODE IN A SIMULATED SOCIAL NETWORK

Clicking on New Policy the user is presented with a form for creating a new policy. The form contains a set of text boxes that the user needs to fill. After submitting the form, it is checked for syntactic correctness of the various fields. If all fields are correct, a new screen with a GUI for specifying a new policy is created, otherwise the system displays the same form as filled by the user and containing a list of messages describing the errors messages that were spotted in the user input.

Selecting any of the listed policies the user can inspect the policy parameters. A top menu allows him to clone this policy, edit its parameters through a GUI or delete the policy.

Politika provides a GUI on the web that allows the designer to create/edit a tree representation of a policy as described in the previous sections. Figure 33 provides a screenshot of this GUI corresponding to the radicalization policy example. The user can click on the tree nodes depicted and examine, edit, delete or execute the clicked node. Executing a node means that the system propagates all design parameters defined on the path from the clicked node to the root to all the nodes belonging to the subtree with the clicked node as root. In addition, the system then automatically creates a bottom-up processing pipeline from all the nodes in this subtree to the clicked node.

FIGURE 33 - SCREENSHOT OF THE POLITIKA GUI FOR MANAGING POLICY HIERARCHIES

In the preceding figure, green, orange, blue and yellow nodes respectively depict policies, goals, objectives and step nodes.

Furthermore, following Figure 34 provides a snapshot of a web-based GUI for visualizing and editing the population network used in policy design, either in 2D or 3D. The visualizer uses several attributes for each node related to visualization (x, y, z, red, green, blue, alpha, radius, scale). As the figure indicates, the user can click on a node in the graph and examine/edit the attributes of the individual corresponding to this node. Furthermore, he can insert/delete nodes/edges in the graph, mainly to fine-tune the population that was generated by the network generation component. Finally, the GUI allows the user to visualize the execution of a social dynamics simulation on the network.

FIGURE 34 - GUI FOR NETWORK DATA MANAGEMENT AND VISUALIZATION OF SIMULATIONS

Demo and Current System Version

A demo video of the current version of Politika is available online⁸ and an experimental version of Politika is also available⁹.

⁸ <https://youtu.be/1lg3FtnCyFM>

⁹ epinoetic.org:4000

2.2.7 Analytical Proxy

This component has been developed during the third phase of the project and thus, it was not included in the previous version of this deliverable.

The analytical proxy provides a unique method that can be invoked and allows the interaction of the overall PolicyCLOUD solution with the external frameworks. It is provided as an analytical function by the DAA layer, and therefore, its interface is invoked indirectly by the latter. As a result, to be able to be invoked by the DAA layer, a main method has been provided that accepts a JsonObject with all related information. As an analytical function, this information is divided into two parts: the user variables and the system configuration parameters.

Regarding the user variables, the analytical function can accept a generic way for defining the required user input, compatible with the data model of the PDT layer, that can be later interpreted by the external analytical framework. For instance, for the case of the Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics, these parameters have been defined as follows:

```
[
  {
    "id": "a3a56fe8-a270-4f34-a28e-2d6ab3c9cb1e",
    "name": "Base_Case",
    "unit": null,
    "description": "The base case policy parameters",
    "valueType": "GENERIC",
    "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
      "EQUAL"
    ],
    "inputType": "VARIABLE",
    "required": true,
    "valueConstraints": []
  },
  {
    "id": "cc7c37a6-c54f-4001-818a-0c8c77239d2f",
    "name": "Alternatives",
    "unit": null,
    "description": "Sampling points for policy",
    "valueType": "GENERIC",
    "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
      "EQUAL"
    ],
    "inputType": "VARIABLE",
    "required": true,
    "valueConstraints": []
  }
]
```

Then, an example of an input defined by the end-user can be depicted as follows:

```
[
  {
    "id": "a3a56fe8-a270-4f34-a28e-2d6ab3c9cb1e",
```



```
"name": "Base_Case",
"unit": null,
"description": "The base case policy parameters",
"valueType": "GENERIC",
"evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"],
"inputType": "VARIABLE",
"required": true,
"value": {
  "type": "EQUAL",
  "value": {
    "name": "fields",
    "list": [
      {"key": "max_price", "value": {"value": 30}},
      {"key": "price_A", "value": {"value": 13}},
      {"key": "price_B", "value": {"value": 11}},
      {"key": "avg_price", "value": {"value": 15}},
      {"key": "quality_A", "value": {"value": 0.89}},
      {"key": "quality_B", "value": {"value": 0.87}},
      {"key": "avg_quality", "value": {"value": 0.85}},
      {"key": "max_income", "value": {"value": 50000}},
      {"key": "ad_intensity_A", "value": {"value": 0.2}},
      {"key": "ad_intensity_B", "value": {"value": 0.2}},
      {"key": "avg_purchase_motivation_A", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "avg_purchase_motivation_B", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "purchase_motivation_ratio", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "purchase_motivation_ratio", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "wine_price_ratio", "value": {"value": -1}},
      {"key": "ad_intensity_ratio", "value": {"value": -1}},
      {"key": "x", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "y", "value": {"value": 0}},
      {"key": "z", "value": {"value": 0}}
    ]
  }
},
"valueConstraints": [],
{
  "id": "cc7c37a6-c54f-4001-818a-0c8c77239d2f",
  "name": "Alternatives",
  "unit": null,
  "description": "Sampling points for policy",
  "valueType": "GENERIC",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"],
  "inputType": "VARIABLE",
  "required": true,
  "value": {
    "type": "GENERIC",
    "values": [
      {
        "name": "option1", "list": [
          {"key": "price_A", "value": {"value": 13}},
          {"key": "ad_intensity_ratio_A", "value": {"value": 0.2}}
        ]
      },
      {
        "name": "option2", "list": [
          {"key": "price_A", "value": {"value": 9}},
          {"key": "ad_intensity_A", "value": {"value": 0.2}}
        ]
      },
      {
        "name": "option3", "list": [
          {"key": "price_B", "value": {"value": 10}},
          {"key": "ad_intensity_A", "value": {"value": 0.4}},
          {"key": "ad_intensity_B", "value": {"value": 0.8}}
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```
    }  
  ]  
},  
"valueConstraints": []  
}  
]
```

This input will be received from the main method of the analytical proxy via the DAA layer into the aforementioned `JsonObject`. The analytical proxy itself is unaware of the values of the parameters. It is the responsibility of the external analytical frameworks to interpret this input accordingly.

The result of this invocation will be the result of the external analytical framework, as described in the previous subsection, that will be eventually stored to the PDT backend, so that it can be retrieved and visualised to the end users.

2.2.8 Operational Data Repository

2.2.8.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPERATIONAL DATA REPOSITORY

During the third period of the project, focus was given on the enhancement of the operational data repository with the Seamless Analytical Framework, whose purpose is to provide a unique point for submitting queries over federated datasets. That is, over a dataset that is split between two different datastores: the operational one that contains fresh data and a data warehouse that contains obsolete or historical data.

2.2.8.2 OPERATIONAL DATA REPOSITORY: INTERFACE DOCUMENTATION

The operational data repository provides various interfaces for data connectivity that can be used in different scenarios. Firstly, it implements the JDBC interface, which is a standard specified under the Java JSR-221¹⁰. JDBC allows for a connection with the SQL query engine of the operational data repository, where the data user can exploit the SQL query language to perform complex query statements supported by the rich capabilities of the SQL itself. Currently, the JDBC driver of the operational datastore supports the execution of the standard SQL statements, under its current ISO SQL:2016.

In addition to JDBC, an implementation of the OData¹¹ specification has been provided, which is an OASIS standard that allows the connection to a data store via well-defined REST API. It allows for the integration of components incompatible with JDBC and cannot usually open direct connections to a datastore, rather than should communicate via HTTP messages.

Moreover, the operational data repository provides a direct API that allows to directly open connections to the storage engine of LXS. The latter provide rich query capabilities like SQL; however, it cannot support JOIN operations. The benefit of directly connecting to the storage is that both data connections and query executions are performed much more efficiently, as direct connection permits to bypass the query engine layer. This is crucial in cases where very low latency is a requirement, such as to support

¹⁰ <https://jcp.org/en/jsr/detail?id=221>

¹¹ <https://www.odata.org/documentation/>

data ingestion at very high rates. In this second phase of the project, this direct API has been released, written in Java and packaged as a library into a Jar file. It contains the JNI binding that allows Java code to invoke native code written in C. The interface is like the ones used by popular document-based datastores, such as MongoDB.

In order to connect, the application developer has to firstly open a *session* providing the details for data connectivity, such as the URL and port of the datastore, the logical database name and user specific credentials as the following code snippet depicts:

```
Settings settings = Settings.parse("lx://lxserver:9876/db@APP");
// you can overwrite any connection property
settings.add("URL", "kivi:lxis://lxserver:9876");
settings.add("DATABASE", "db");
settings.add("USER", user);

Session session = SessionFactory.newSession(settings);
Database database = session.database();
```

The application developer needs to first define the *settings* of the connection, thus the connection URL, username etc, and then to create a new *session* from which it can request the logical database to perform operations upon. Once the *database* object has been created, the application developer can use it to get access to specific data tables and insert new records to it. This happens by defining the data item to be inserted, the *tuple*, and inserting the latter to the database, as the following code snippet indicates:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
Tuple person = people.createTuple();

//Fill in tuple fields
person.put("id", 1L)
    .put("name", "John")
    .put("lastName", "Doe")
    .put("phone", "555333695")
    .put("email", "johndoe@nowhere.no")
    .put("birthday", Date.valueOf("1970-01-01"))
    .put("numChildren", 4);

//Insert tuple
people.insert(person);
//Tuples are sent to the datastore when COMMIT is done
session.commit();
```

In cases of an auto-incremented primary key field, the application developer must define a *sequence*. Using the *sequence*, it can get the next auto-incremented value and set it as the primary key of the new record that needs to be inserted. As a result, the code snippet above should be slightly changed to rely on the retrieved value of the *sequence*:

```
long personId = database.getSequence("personId").nextVal();
person.put("id", personId, Long.class )
    .put("name", "John", String.class )
    .put("lastName", "Doe", String.class )
    .put("phone", "555333695", String.class )
```

```
.put("email", "johndoe@nowhere.no", String.class )
.put("birthday",Date.valueOf("1970-01-01"), String.class )
.put("numChildren", 4, String.class );
```

Finally, when binary objects need to be stored, as in the case of the PDT backend, then the BLOB column must use an output stream Java operator to write the byte array, as follows:

```
person.put("name", "John")
        .put("lastName", "Doe")
        .put("phone", "555333695");

OutputStream os = people.createBlob(person, "photo");
Files.copy(Paths.get("/path/to/john.jpeg"), os);
```

For updating/deleting records, first the identifier record that needs to be updated/deleted must be defined using the *TupleKey* object. Then, the corresponding methods of the *table* class should be invoked accordingly, as the following code snippet illustrates:

```
// Tuple person to be updated has to be previously retrieved through a get()
Tuplekey key = table.createTupleKey();
key.put("id", 0L, Long.class );

Tuple person = table.get(key);
person.put("phone", "anotherPhone", String.class )
        .put("email", "johndoe@somewhere.some", String.class )

people.update(person);

//or delete this record
Table people = database.getTable("person");
TupleKey johnKey = people.createTupleKey();
johnKey.put("id", key);
people.delete(johnKey);
```

Finally, reading data can either be done via a get operation over the identifier, or by using a scan operation. For fetching data using a get, the application developer should use a code similar to the following snippet:

```
Tuplekey key = table.createTupleKey();
key.put("id", 0L, Long.class );
Tuple tuple = table.get(key);
```

In this example, again we need to define the corresponding *TupleKey* object and read it using its corresponding *get* operation. However, in cases we want to perform a *scan*, the above code must be changed to the following:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
TupleKey min = people.createTupleKey();
min.put("id", 20);

TupleKey max = people.createTupleKey();
```

```
max.put("id", 30L);

people.find()
    .min(min)
    .max(max)
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));

// Max 20 results
people.find()
    .first(20)
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

In this example, a scan is defined over the primary key of the data table, as the application developer needs to define the upper and lower limit of the dataset to be scanned. Then, the *find* method needs to be invoked, that returns a Java *Iterator*. Using the latter, the application developer can now iterate through the returned data items using the *foreach* clause of Java.

In cases the user needs to scan over columns not defined having primary or secondary indexes, then a *filter* condition must be applied to the *find* method, as the following code snippets depict:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
// Basic comparisons
people.find()
    .filter(gt("numChildren", 4).and(eq("name", string("John"))))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));

// Between
Date minDate = Date.valueOf("1900-01-01");
Date maxDate = Date.valueOf("2000-01-01");

people.find()
    .filter(between("birthday", date(minDate), date(maxDate)))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));

// Using a Expression with operators
people.find()
    .filter(gt("numChildren", sub(field("numRooms"), int(1))))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

In cases the application developer prefers to retrieve a specific list of columns, instead of the whole data item, he or she needs to perform a *projection* over the returned dataset. This can be also defined in the *find* method, as the following code snippet indicates.

```
String[] fields = {"name", "lastName", "birthDay"};
people.find()
    .project(include(fields))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        String name = tuple.get("name", String.class );
        String lastname = tuple.get("lastName", String.class );
        Date date = tuple.get("birthDay", Date.class );
    });

// SELECT name, Lastname, weight/height^2 AS imc FROM person
```

```
// Alias and expression usage
ProjectionExpression[] projExp = {
    alias("name"),
    alias("lastName")
};

people.find()
    .project(compose(projExp))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        String name = tuple.get("name", String.class );
        String lastName = tuple.get("lastName", String.class );
    });
```

Finally, the direct API can perform aggregate operations over the data tables. The application developer must define an initial array with the fields to be used as the group by the key (if any), and then a list of aggregation expressions over some fields. This is illustrated in the following code snippet:

```
// SELECT name, department, salary, sum(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department) AS
totalSalary
// FROM employees
employees.find()
    .project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").sum("totalSalary", "salary")))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
        String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
        Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
        Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("totalSalary", Long.class );
    });
// SELECT name, department, salary, sum(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department
ORDER BY salary) AS totalSalary
// FROM employees
employees.find()
    .project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").sum("totalSalary", "salary").orderBy("salary"))
    )
    .forEach(tuple->{
        Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
        String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
        Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
        Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("totalSalary", Long.class );
    });

// SELECT name, department, salary, max(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS maxSalary FROM employees
employees.find()
    .project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").max("maxSalary", "salary")))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
        String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
        Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
        Long maxSalary = tuple.get("maxSalary", Long.class );
    });
```

```
// SELECT name, department, salary, min(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS minSalary FROM employees
employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").min("minSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long minSalary = tuple.get("minSalary", Long.class );
});

// SELECT name, department, salary, count(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS countSalary FROM employees
employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").count("countSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("countSalary", Long.class );
});

// SELECT name, department, salary, avg(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS avgSalary FROM employees
employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept",
"salary").addWindow(window("dept").avg("avgSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
double departmentSalary = tuple.get("avgSalary", Double.class );
});
```

Having the direct API released, now the data scientist can exploit the benefits of the direct connection to the storage and the lower latency of the query execution, using the already implemented connectors to popular data/streaming processing frameworks, such as Apache Spark¹² and Apache Flink¹³. Due to this, the data scientist can use the API of those frameworks, and those will make use of the direct API, through the connectors implemented and provided by the operational datastore.

2.2.8.3 SEAMLESS ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK: INTERFACE DOCUMENTATION

As it has been already mentioned, the Seamless Analytical Framework provides a unique point of access to a federated dataset that has been split into two different types of datastore. The access point is the operational data repository that has been enhanced with this functionality. The operational data repository is a SQL compliant relational datastore. It can be accessed via the direct API that was described

¹² [Apache Spark™ - Unified Engine for large-scale data analytics](#)

¹³ [Apache Flink: Stateful Computations over Data Streams](#)

in the previous subsection or using its standards JDBC connectivity mechanism. The latter connects with its internal relational query engine, thus allows the data user to submit query statements in this standard manner.

The implementation of the Seamless Analytical Framework is based on the Java's table functions that can be considered as additional query operators that perform a specific type of processing. As such, they can be combined with other relational algebraic operations to compose a more complicated query execution plan. As a result, a query that can be used as an example to demonstrate the use of the Seamless Analytical Framework will be similar to a standard SQL statement, with the difference that it makes use of the queryfederator table function, which implements the functionality needed by this enhancement. This can be depicted in the following example statement:

```
SELECT
count(*)
FROM table("queryfederator"('
SELECT PRODUCTS.COD_ART_INTEGER, PRODUCTS.DESC_N1, FEEDBACK.ID_FEEDBACK, FEEDBACK.EVENT
FROM PRODUCTS INNER JOIN FEEDBACK ON PRODUCTS.COD_ART = FEEDBACK.COD_ART',
'COD_ART_INTEGER INTEGER, PRODUCTS.DESC_N1 VARCHAR, ID_FEEDBACK INTEGER, EVENT VARCHAR',
'jdbc:hive2://127.0.0.1:10000',
'8192',
'4'
))
```

In this statement, we combine a relational algebraic operation (in our case the count) with the result of our table function. The count operation accepts a relation as its input and returns the number of its tuples. The input relation will be the output our table function named queryfederator. The latter accepts 3 mandatory and 2 optional requirements:

- query statement: this will be a standard SQL statement whose execution will be upon a federated dataset that has been split into the two datastores. The details of how this query execution will be processed is internal to the implementation of the Seamless Analytical Framework, and as such, the latter returns transparently to the user the equivalent result, as the whole data was stored in to the operational datastore.
- schema definition: this includes the definition of the schema of the returned relation. This is required by the relational query engine of the operational data repository in order for the latter to perform the necessary data mappings and validate the integrity and correctness of the submitted statement.
- remote url: this is the connection string to the second datastore, where the historical data has been migrated. It is used by the Seamless Analytical Framework to be capable of connecting to the remote datastore.
- batch size: this is the size of each batch of data that will be sent to the external dataset when transforming the join operator to an IN clause.
- concurrent connections: this is the number of parallel connections to the external dataset that will receive the aforementioned batches when executing the join operation transformed to the IN clause.

2.3 Baseline technologies and tools

This section describes the baseline technologies and tools under the delivered components.

2.3.1 DAA API Gateway

2.3.1.1 KUBERNETES

Kubernetes¹⁴ is the leading open-source container management platform used in production of growing number of enterprises as the base of private on-prem cloud, as well as offered by almost all cloud providers as a managed dedicated cluster, and as described in D4.5 [3] it is the chosen underlying platform for all PolicyCloud components. The underlying software components of DAA, both OpenWhisk and Kafka, have been deployed on a Kubernetes cluster over the PolicyCloud testbed h.

2.3.1.2 KAFKA

Apache Kafka¹⁵ is used as a transformation buffer to store intermediate data between components in a reliable and asynchronous way. As in SW2, communication between functions is done through OpenWhisk, in the future in case the OpenWhisk limitations of input and output size (1MB) to actions would not be adequate, Kafka will be used as the intermediate buffering between functions as well.

The LeanXcale database interface has been implemented in the components integration phase using Kafka connector to insert the PolicyCloud processed datasets into the LeanXcale database backend (h).

2.3.1.3 OPENWHISK

Apache OpenWhisk¹⁶ is an open source lightweight serverless platform that provides capability to deploy functions (written in any language) and specify triggers and rules by which the functions are executed. It offers a simple programming model where the function developer can concentrate only on the mere logic of the function, while the deployment and activation details are taken care of transparently. It is based on containers as the functions' wrapper and deploys and integrates perfectly in a Kubernetes environment. All analytic functions in PolicyCLOUD will be deployed as OpenWhisk actions, with appropriate triggers and activation rules, addressing the extensibility and reusability requirements. Additional important capability of OpenWhisk is the composition of functions to be activated per trigger/rule, which enable to specify a pipeline of analytic functions to be applied to a data source.

The DAA APIs are implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk cluster), web actions were written to expose functions and data sources APIs with REST, implemented in node.js

Packages and package-bindings were implemented to store metadata and pass it as parameters in functions invocations.

¹⁴ <https://kubernetes.io>

¹⁵ <https://kafka.apache.org>

¹⁶ <https://OpenWhisk.apache.org>

Triggers, rules, and Kafka feed were used to subscribe to topics and apply data transformation functions as data enters the platform and is available.

Analytic functions are implemented using OpenWhisk actions. Sample reference functions were written in java and packaged in jar according to OpenWhisk actions guidelines and implement the connectivity to the LeanXcale database as backend.

2.3.1.4 GITLAB AND CONTAINER REGISTRY

Used to store project's WP4 DAA files, reference implementation and image container registry.

2.3.1.5 LOGSTASH

A centralized logging for PolicyCLOUD was implemented with a standard logging service by deploying logstash¹⁷, arguably the most popular open-source log management tool, on PolicyCLOUD's Kubernetes infrastructure. The logging service is accessible to all PolicyCLOUD WPs using an HTTP API, and forms a centralized, project-wide infrastructure component. Each logging event is stored in a persistent file system enabled by NFS and ensures resiliency to pod failures and restarts.

2.3.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.3.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The Data Cleaning component is developed with Python 3.7 using the Flask python micro web framework¹⁸. Flask is a powerful framework written in Python and based on the Werkzeug¹⁹ toolkit and Jinja2²⁰ template engine that is independent from libraries or tools and that supports a large list of extensions for application features. Besides the Flask framework, a list of libraries and tools has been used in the context of the Data Cleaning to support several functionalities of the component. For the data structure handling Pandas²¹ has been selected, NumPy²² is used for all the numerical computations, while for the streaming data diverse nlp libraries and tools have been exploited (e.g., spacy).

2.3.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

For the implementation and utilization of the first sub-component of the Enhanced Interoperability component, different technologies and techniques from the fields of NLP and Semantic Web were utilized. To this end, the overall code was implemented based on Python3²³ programming language. Moreover, spaCy²⁴ framework was utilized to perform concrete and high accuracy NLP sub-tasks, such as Tokenization, Sentence splitting, POS tagging, NER etc., which are core tasks in the provided sub-component and their importance and overall functionality have introduced in previous sections. On top

¹⁷ <https://www.elastic.co/logstash/>

¹⁸ <http://flask.pocoo.org/>

¹⁹ <http://werkzeug.pocoo.org/>

²⁰ <http://jinja.pocoo.org/>

²¹ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

²² <http://www.numpy.org/>

²³ <https://www.python.org>

²⁴ <https://spacy.io/>

of this, NLP tasks integrate with Semantic Web technologies to provide a hybrid approach through the utilization of state-of-the-art SemAI mechanism. To this end, SPARQL²⁵, a widely used RDF query language, is being utilized. The latter is being used to perform queries on Wikidata Knowledge base to identify and interlink appropriate entities based on the ones that have already been recognised from the raw texts. Moreover, the gensim²⁶ library is being utilized under the scopes of the Topic Identification subtasks in order to provide the three (3) models for this specific task. Finally, the Neo4J²⁷ graph database is being used in the Ontology Mapping subtask to provide to the system the ability to store the semantic annotations and relationships of the provided data.

2.3.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

The SKA-EDA component has been built using Python and well-known data analysis libraries such as Pandas²⁸. On other hand, in terms of integration this component is built as a data workflow using Apache NiFi²⁹, a powerful tool that allows us to create reusable modules and use them in data workflows easily. In collaboration with Apache NiFi Registry to maintain the versions of the workflows developed, and to ease the process of exporting and importing the workflows in an automated way. To execute the Apache NiFi workflows in an automated way without the GUI, the Python client SDK NiPyApi³⁰ are used. This client permits to connect to different Apache NiFi instances, export and import workflows, execute, and configure those workflows, and get the status of them, among others. Finally, in terms of deployment, all the services which take part of the SKA-EDA are accessing using a nginx server³¹ used in parallel with uwsgi³². Nginx server is executed in a docker³³ container that also contains the source code of the component (microservices documented in “User Interfaces for SKA-EDA” section).

The SKA-TSF component have been developed in python, using Flask³⁴ as the framework to serve the implemented functionalities as REST services using swagger. To allow the access to the offered services, nginx server³⁵ is used in parallel with uwsgi³⁶. Nginx server is executed in a docker³⁷ container that also contains the source code of the component to ease the deployment of the backend of the analytics implemented (microservices documented in “User Interfaces for SKA-TSF” section).

²⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query>

²⁶ <https://radimrehurek.com/gensim/>

²⁷ <https://neo4j.com/>

²⁸ [pandas - Python Data Analysis Library \(pydata.org\)](https://pandas.pydata.org/)

²⁹ <https://nifi.apache.org/>

³⁰ <https://nipyapi.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

³¹ <https://www.nginx.com/>

³² <https://uwsgi-docs.readthedocs.io/>

³³ <https://www.docker.com/>

³⁴ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/>

³⁵ <https://www.nginx.com/>

³⁶ <https://uwsgi-docs.readthedocs.io/>

³⁷ <https://www.docker.com/>

2.3.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

Both trend and sentiment analysis components have been developed in python, using Flask³⁸ as the framework to serve the implemented functionalities as REST services using swagger. To allow the access to the offered services, nginx server³⁹ is used in parallel with uwsgi⁴⁰. Nginx server is executed in a docker⁴¹ container that also contains the source code of the component to ease the deployment of the backend of the analytics implemented.

In the sentiment analysis scenario, AspectBasedSentimentAnalysis library⁴² was finally used. That library provides the core functionality to generate sentiment score for the different aspects that appear in a given text.

For the trend analysis scenario, initially owlready2⁴³ was used to navigate through some ontologies provided with the modelization of the scenarios. Nevertheless, due to the diversity of formats of the modelization of the use cases received, these modelizations were translated into an excel table and loaded. To interact with the data persistence backend, sqlalchemy⁴⁴ and leanxcale drivers⁴⁵ for sqlalchemy were included in the trend analysis component.

2.3.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

Politika has been implemented using the following baseline technologies:

- Elixir/Erlang⁴⁶
- Phoenix Web Framework⁴⁷
- D3.js⁴⁸

2.3.6 Operational Data Repository

The operational data repository consists of various components and tools, each one built over different baseline technologies and tools. More precisely, it consists of:

- The adaptable and distributed storage engine: It has been written in C and provides the capabilities for persistent storage of data elements.

³⁸ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/>

³⁹ <https://www.nginx.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://uwsgi-docs.readthedocs.io/>

⁴¹ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁴² <https://github.com/ScalaConsultants/Aspect-Based-Sentiment-Analysis>

⁴³ <https://owlready2.readthedocs.io/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.sqlalchemy.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://docs.leanxcale.com/leanxcale/1.9/development/python/index.html>

⁴⁶ <https://elixir-lang.org/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.phoenixframework.org/>

⁴⁸ <https://d3js.org/>

- The transactional processing mechanism: It enables support for transactions and ensures ACID properties. It can be scaled out linearly and it has been completely implemented in Java 8.
- The query engine: It provides support for executing queries written in SQL scripting language. It has been implemented in Java 8 and makes use of the Apache Calcite query processing framework, which lies in its core and extends its functionality to provide fully SQL support.
- The monitoring engine: It makes use of the Prometheus monitoring framework for gathering metrics and monitoring information by each of its components. All components expose monitoring information to specific URIs where custom exporters are placing data that can be imported by Prometheus. Additionally, the openwizard.io framework is being used for exporting custom monitoring information (i.e., query compilation time) via JMX extensions.
- The monitoring dashboard: It makes use of the Grafana Dashboard for visualizing the monitoring information gathered by Prometheus.
- Ansible: An ansible installer is provided that automatically installs various components in a target infrastructure (either a virtual one via the use of containers, or over bare metal) .

3. Source code

3.1 Availability

This section provides the links and access information to the actual code repositories.

3.1.1 DAA API Gateway

Software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD's github which is accessible to the members of the consortium and includes DAA code to deploy in OpenWhisk.

Gitlab: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oshrit/daa/>

Container registry: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oshrit/daa/container_registry

3.1.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

3.1.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The software prototype of the Data Cleaning is provided in PolicyCLOUD's GitLab repository and can be found under the URL:

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

3.1.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

Software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD's Gitlab repository, which is accessible to the members of the consortium, under the URL below:

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

3.1.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

Regarding the SKA-EDA, the code is available at:

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/exploratoryanalysis> and has the following folder structure:

- integration, contains the Python actions for all the distributions.
- microservice, contains the services that provide the core functionality which server the Python actions.

Regarding the SKA-TSF the code is available at

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/timeseriesforecasting/> with the following folder structure:

- integration, contains the Python actions for the sarima prediction and for the prophet prediction.
- microservice, contains the services that provide the core functionality which server the Python actions.
- notebook, contains the Jupyter notebooks used along all the development.

3.1.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

The code for the sentiment analysis component is available at <http://snf-877903.vm.oceanos.grnet.gr/jorge/sentimentanalysis> and has the next folder structure:

- **Root:** description of the git project and details in the requirements and steps needed to deploy it.
- **Functions:** folder that contains the python code to execute the sentiment and the aggregate functions.
 - nifi-sentiment-aggregator-lxc.py (new)
 - nifi-sentiment-ingest.py
- **Installation:** folder with a docker-compose file to deploy an Apache NiFi instance.
- **Microservice:** Directory with all the logic of the component (microsentiment.py), including a Dockerfile and configuration files to dockerize the analytical component.
- **Scripts:** three python files to export/import/execute an Apache NiFi workflow, and one python file to set the Apache NiFi Registry.

[1] nifi-execute-flow.py

- nifi-export-flow.py
- nifi-import-flow.py
- nifi-add-registry.py
- **Templates:** the exported version of the two Apache NiFi workflows that represent the two functions described in the component.
 - nipyapi-sentiment-aggregator-lxc-flow.json (new)
 - nipyapi-sentiment-ingest-flow.json

The code for the Trend analysis component is available at REPOSITORY URL with the following structure:

- **Microservice:** This directory contains all the logic to deploy the trend analysis component as a docker container by means of using the Dockerfile file.
 - useCases: This directory contains the needed scripts to initialise a use case that is going to make use of this analytical tool in the POLICYCLOUD project. As has been mentioned in the definition of the trend analysis tool, this tool requires the modelization of the entities and relations that take part in the use case. This directory contains the modelization of both SARGA and MAGGIOLI use cases as well as the script (UseCaseInit.py) that initialises the databases (populating them with the data from those modelizations).

3.1.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

The code for the current Politika prototype resides in epinoetic.org/Politika/politika_demo_v2.tar.gz. The code for the server running the integration with PolicyCLOUD via a REST API resides in: epinoetic.org/Politika/politika_api.zip

3.1.6 Analytical proxy

The source code of the analytical proxy is open and available from the project's private GitLab repository that can be found at: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/analytical-proxy

3.1.7 Operational Data Repository

The source code of the operational datastore is based on the background technology that LXS is bringing to the project and is therefore proprietary. Therefore, the source code for this component cannot be provided to the consortium. Instead, LXS provides precompiled and pre-packaged binaries that can be used instead, containing all functionality developed so far. The binaries are accessible to the members of the consortium and have been uploaded in the private GitLab repository that can be found at: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/policy-store

The pre-packaged binaries now include the enhancements added during this third phase of the project, related with the Seamless Analytical Framework.

The GitLab repository additionally contains scripting files that allow the creation of a docker image that contains the LXS datastore distribution, so that the application developer or data scientist can run it locally for testing/experimentation purposes. This docker image is also being used by the Kubernetes cluster in order to deploy the data repository to be used by the integrated PolicyCLOUD solution.

3.2 Exploitation

This section provides information about where components are deployed and how they can be accessed and run.

3.2.1 DAA API Gateway

Setup of DAA prototype environment:

1. Install Kubernetes cluster ⁴⁹
2. Install OpenWhisk and Kafka on the k8s cluster ⁵⁰
3. Follow LeanXcale installation in section 3.2.6, run the docker image as `docker run -d -p 1529:1529 --name datastore policy-store:latest`
4. Setup OpenWhisk environment:
 - 4.1. Git clone DAA code from Section 3.1.1
 - 4.2. Create namespace policycloud

⁴⁹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/tools/>

⁵⁰ <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk-deploy-kube>

4.3. Create package daa

4.4. Create the web actions components for data source and analytic functions:

4.4.1.wsk package update daa -p brokers '['10.111.3.60:9092\']' -p accessToken 897df16803b16d34a750c79fde5d120d2dff31d5 -p repo policycloud -p branch master -p owner OSHRITF (Supply the gitlab credentials to the package creation)

4.4.2.to pull node-modules run: npm install .

4.4.3.create analytic function web action zip file: zip -r action.zip

4.4.4.wsk action update /policycloud/daa/analytic-function ./analytic-function/action.zip --kind nodejs:10 -a provide-api-key true --web true

4.4.5.create data sources web action file: zip -r action.zip

4.4.6.wsk action update /policycloud/daa/datasource ./datasource/action.zip --kind nodejs:10 -a provide-api-key true --web true

Python and Java reference sample functions can be found in the repository (src/main), source code and packaged for use in OpenWhisk. Those are provided as examples to assist analytic owners to write their ingest/analytic functions.

3.2.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

3.2.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The Data Cleaning software prototype is a Python project. As a result, to be able to run the prototype manually, Python should be properly preinstalled and preconfigured on the system and PYTHONPATH should include all the modules of the Data Cleaner prototype. To facilitate the exploitation process, the source code must be downloaded from the repository, and then has to be opened as a Python project in the preferred IDE. On top of that, since various of the used modules are not pre-installed, the user has to manually install them. To do so, the user must use the de facto standard package-management system used to install and manage software packages written in Python (pip). In that case, the user must run a cmd.exe terminal with the current Python environment, and write the following commands:

Installing pandas-schema

```
$ pip install pandas-schema
```

Installing flask

```
$ pip install flask
```

Installing library for language detection

```
$ pip install langdetect
```

Installing library for emojis

```
$ pip install emoji
```

Installing spacy tool for spanish language

```
$ python -m spacy download es_core_news_sm
```

Installing spacy tool for english language

```
$ python -m spacy download en_core_web_sm
```

Installing library for NLP processes

```
$ pip install nltk
```

As soon as this process gets complete, the user must simply run the program in a development server, since it is the first version of the prototype, and visit the following URL in a web browser:

<http://127.0.0.1:5000/cleaning>

This will start the Data Cleaner prototype as a web application and the exposed external interface will be available at *localhost:5000*.

3.2.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

As analyzed in the previous section several dependencies and tools must be fulfilled and installed in order the provided code to be executed. First, some prerequisites need to be fulfilled so that the user can execute the NLP subtasks that are incorporated in this component. To this end, Python3 and pip installer⁵¹ should be properly preinstalled and preconfigured on the system. Finally, availability of the Neo4j graph database is a prerequisite for the use of the Ontology Mapping subtask.

What is more, below there is a list of all the wanted tools and libraries and their installation guides.

Installing Neo4j

```
$ pip install neo4j
```

Installation of the neo4j package for the Python language to be able to perform queries and have data integration with the powerful Neo4j graph database.

Installing spaCy

SpaCy can easily being installed via a pip installer, which is utilized to install Python libraries, and the following statement:

```
$ pip install -U spacy
```

Otherwise, if Anaconda tool is already installed in the machine the following command on the Anaconda prompt needs to be executed:

```
$ conda install -c conda-forge spacy
```

⁵¹ <https://pip.pypa.io/en/stable/>

Once the spaCy has been downloaded and installed, the next step is to download the language model, which in this case is the English language model. The language model is utilized to perform a variety of NLP tasks, which were introduced in previous sections. To this end, the following command downloads the appropriate language model:

```
$ python -m spacy download en
```

Installing qwikidata

A Python package with tools that allow to integrate and interact the provided data with Wikidata. The package defines a set of classes that allow to represent Wikidata entities, which is being utilized by the Interoperability component to interlink recognized entities from raw texts with Wikidata entities with the ultimate goal to extract JSON URI annotated data. This specific tool can be executed only in machines and environments with installed Python 3.5 or newer versions. Moreover, this package incorporates SPARQL and gives the availability to the end user to utilize SPARQL queries.

The most recent version of this package can be installed by using pip installer, *\$ pip install qwikidata*

As soon as the above processes and installations get complete, the user must simply run the program in a development server, and visit the following URL in a web browser:

<http://127.0.0.1:5000/interoperability>

This will start the Enhanced Interoperability prototype as a web application and the exposed external interface will be available at *localhost:5000*.

3.2.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

For this prototype, the functionalities described for these components have been deployed in a private environment. However, it can be replicated following the instructions and files provided in the git repository.

3.2.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

The functionalities expected for this component will be deployed in a private environment. However, it can be replicated following the instructions and files that will be provided in the git repository.

3.2.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

Politika is currently deployed at the GRNet cloud. It can be accessed at: <http://epinoetic.org:4000>

The installation instructions that follow refer to a Linux machine and have been tested with the Ubuntu distribution.

- To install Erlang, Elixir, Phoenix and Postgres follow the instructions at:
 - <https://hexdocs.pm/phoenix/installation.html>
- Extract the politika_demo.zip file. A politika_demo directory will appear at the site of extraction.

- Open with a text editor (e.g., gedit) the `politika_demo/config/config.exs` file and update the following text section with the credentials for the Postgres installation in your system assuming that Postgres runs locally using port 5432 (otherwise update the fields `hostname:` and `port:` accordingly):
 - `config :politika, Politika.Repo,`
 - `database: "politika",`
 - `username: "XXXXXXXXX",`
 - `password: "XXXXXXXXX",`
 - `hostname: "localhost",`
 - `port: "5432"`
- Open a terminal window go to the `politika_demo` directory and setup the database from within ecto by typing:
 - `mix ecto.create`
 - `mix ecto.migrate`
- Run the `politika` system by typing in the `politika_demo` directory:
 - `mix phx.server`
- The system will start running in your machine at port 4000. For example, you can access Politika by typing the following address in your browser:
 - `http://<Your IP address>:4000`

3.2.6 Analytical Proxy

The analytical proxy is provided as a built-in functionality of the overall integrated PolicyCLOUD solution. To use it, one has first to configure it property using the DAA layer. This can be done using the DAA interface, as for every other function. An example invocation can be depicted as follows:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '
```

```
{
  "kind": "java:8",
  "name": "Policy-Simulator-UX",
  "filename": "analytical-proxy-1.0-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar",
  "main": "eu.policycloud.analytical.proxy.AnalyticalProxy",
  "function_conf_parameters":
  [{"proxy_url": "http://epinoetic.org:5000/api/pol", "method": "POST"},
  {"function_parameters": [{"id": "a3a56fe8-a270-4f34-a28e-2d6ab3c9cb1e", "name": "Base_Case", "unit": null, "description": "The base case policy parameters", "valueType": "GENERIC", "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"], "inputType": "VARIABLE", "required": true, "valueConstraints": []}, {"id": "cc7c37a6-c54f-4001-818a-0c8c77239d2f", "name": "Alternatives", "unit": null, "description": "Sampling points for policy", "valueType": "GENERIC", "evaluationTypesAllowed": ["EQUAL"], "inputType": "VARIABLE", "required": true, "valueConstraints": []}],
  "graph": [
    "HEATMAPTABLECHART"
  ]
},
```

```
"policydomain": ["AGRIFOOD"],  
"type": "analytic-analysis",  
"category": "external",  
"description": "It makes use of Politika, an external framework",  
"biasDoc": "For the bias analysis please refer to the external framework of  
Politika",  
"tradeoffsDoc": "For the tradeoffs explanation please refer to the external framework  
of Politika"  
}'
```

As the invocation with its input body is the same as explained in previous sections, the only that needs to be highlighted here is the function configuration parameters:

- proxy_url: this is the URL of the REST API of the external analytical framework that needs to be called
- method: this can be either a POST, or GET

We also need to highlight the function parameters of this registration. In our example we used the same ones that we demonstrate in section 2.1.1.

3.2.7 Operational Data Repository

To use the operational data repository, it is highly recommended to make use of a docker container. Firstly, the user needs to download the current version of the binaries by executing the following:

```
git clone https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/policy-store
```

Then assuming the docker is already installed in the host machine, he or she needs to create the corresponding docker image, by executing the following:

```
docker build -t policy-store.
```

After building the image, he or she can check that it is available in the host machine's docker catalogue. To start the container, he or she would need to execute the following:

```
docker run -d -p 2181:2181 -p 1529:1529 --name datastore --env KVPEXTERNALIP='datastore!9800' policy-  
store {image_id}
```

This will create a single container running in the background where the data store will be installed and start in an all-in-one fashion. It is important to notice the `-p 1529:1529` parameter that exposes the 1529 port to the host machine, so that it can be reachable by another process outside of the container that has access to the network of the host machine.

To connect to the container via the console, she should execute the following:

```
docker exec -it policy-store bash
```

Then, he or she should be able to verify that all components are up and running, by executing the following: `/${BASEDIR}/LX-BIN/bin/lxConsole 3`

4. Conclusion

We provided in this last deliverable of the PolicyCLOUD software demonstrators series a description of the software components which relate to the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer. They provide the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform. At M34 of the project, October 2022, the provided demonstrators are integrated for all end-to-end scenarios including integration with the external Politika platform for 2 use cases. Almost 2 years after the initial usage of the DAA, we can state that it is well adapted to its purpose as it accommodated all the analytics functions needed for all the use cases. In addition, it was also easy to build the integration of external frameworks by using the regular DAA capabilities.

Also, the number of integrated functions for ingest analytics as well as analytics at rest has been increased and our hope in the usage of PolicyCLOUD after the completion of the project is that they will cover many additional use cases for which no additional functions will be needed. This obviously will have to be further checked.

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5. Appendix

We detail in the appendix the long JSONs mentioned in section

5.1 Conceptualizer Output

5.1.1 Conceptualizer Output JSON example

```
{
  "id": "982347272",
  "text": "delegator Veraton LaLanneGranReserva 12LunasGarnacha linkslands ashy
mesally ViñasViejasPaniza locater",
  "created_at": "2022-03-11T07:54:00.000Z",
  "geo": "GR",
  "retweet_count": 6,
  "fav_count": 4,
  "lang": "cn",
  "annotations": [
    {
      "tweet_id": "982347272",
      "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-
20031209/wine#12LunasGarnacha",
      "explicit": true,
      "sentiment": "positive",
      "sentiment_score": 0.9891356583684683,
      "starts": 5,
      "end": 6,
      "probability": 0.9,
      "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
      "type": "PRODUCT"
    },
    {
      "tweet_id": "982347272",
      "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-
20031209/wine#ViñasViejasPaniza",
      "explicit": true,
      "sentiment": "positive",
      "sentiment_score": 0.976182235404849,
      "starts": 9,
      "end": 10,
      "probability": 0.75,
      "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
      "type": "PRODUCT"
    },
    {
      "tweet_id": "982347272",
      "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-
20031209/wine#LaLanneGranReserva",
      "explicit": true,
      "sentiment": "positive",
      "sentiment_score": 0.9872005619108677,
      "starts": 5,
```



```
"end": 6,
"probability": 0.61,
"type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
"type": "PRODUCT"
},
{
"tweet_id": "982347272",
"item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Veraton",
"explicit": true,
"sentiment": "positive",
"sentiment_score": 0.9959542264696211,
"starts": 1,
"end": 2,
"probability": 0.61,
"type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
"type": "PRODUCT"
},
{
"tweet_id": "982347272",
"item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AragonRegion",
"explicit": false,
"sentiment": null,
"sentiment_score": null,
"starts": 5,
"end": 6,
"probability": 0.9,
"type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Region",
"type": "PRODUCT"
},
{
"tweet_id": "982347272",
"item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#DO_Somontano",
"explicit": false,
"sentiment": null,
"sentiment_score": null,
"starts": 5,
"end": 6,
"probability": 0.9,
"type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Region",
"type": "PRODUCT"
},
{
"tweet_id": "982347272",
"item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#GrilloLuna",
"explicit": false,
"sentiment": null,
"sentiment_score": null,
"starts": 5,
"end": 6,
"probability": 0.9,
"type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Winery",
"type": "PRODUCT"
},
},
```

```
{
  "tweet_id": "982347272",
  "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#DO_Cariñena",
  "explicit": false,
  "sentiment": null,
  "sentiment_score": null,
  "starts": 9,
  "end": 10,
  "probability": 0.75,
  "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Region",
  "type": "PRODUCT"
}
```

5.1.2 Conceptualizer Output Validation Schema

```
{
  "definitions": {},
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "https://example.com/object1663781014.json",
  "title": "Root",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "id",
    "text",
    "created_at",
    "geo",
    "retweet_count",
    "fav_count",
    "lang",
    "annotations"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "id": {
      "$id": "#root/id",
      "title": "Id",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "982347272"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    },
    "text": {
      "$id": "#root/text",
      "title": "Text",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        ""
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    }
  }
}
```



```
},
"created_at": {
  "$id": "#root/created_at",
  "title": "Created_at",
  "type": "string",
  "default": "",
  "examples": [
    "2022-03-11T07:54:00.000Z"
  ],
  "pattern": "^.*$"
},
"geo": {
  "$id": "#root/geo",
  "title": "Geo",
  "type": "string",
  "default": "",
  "examples": [
    "GR"
  ],
  "pattern": "^.*$"
},
"retweet_count": {
  "$id": "#root/retweet_count",
  "title": "Retweet_count",
  "type": "integer",
  "examples": [
    6
  ],
  "default": 0
},
"fav_count": {
  "$id": "#root/fav_count",
  "title": "Fav_count",
  "type": "integer",
  "examples": [
    4
  ],
  "default": 0
},
"lang": {
  "$id": "#root/lang",
  "title": "Lang",
  "type": "string",
  "default": "",
  "examples": [
    "cn"
  ],
  "pattern": "^.*$"
},
"annotations": {
  "$id": "#root/annotations",
  "title": "Annotations",
  "type": "array",
  "default": [],
  "items": {
```



```
"$id": "#root/annotations/items",
"title": "Items",
"type": "object",
"required": [
  "tweet_id",
  "item_uri",
  "explicit",
  "sentiment",
  "sentiment_score",
  "starts",
  "end",
  "probability",
  "type_uri",
  "type"
],
"properties": {
  "tweet_id": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/tweet_id",
    "title": "Tweet_id",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "982347272"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "item_uri": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/item_uri",
    "title": "Item_uri",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "http://wikiwiki.com/linkslands"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "explicit": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/explicit",
    "title": "Explicit",
    "type": "boolean",
    "examples": [
      false
    ],
    "default": true
  },
  "sentiment": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/sentiment",
    "title": "Sentiment",
    "type": [
      "string",
      "null"
    ],
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "positive"
    ]
  }
}
```



```
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "sentiment_score": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/sentiment_score",
    "title": "Sentiment_score",
    "type": [
      "number",
      "null"
    ],
    "examples": [
      0.49
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "starts": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/starts",
    "title": "Starts",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      5
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "end": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/end",
    "title": "End",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      6
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "probability": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/probability",
    "title": "Probability",
    "type": "number",
    "examples": [
      0.49
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "type_uri": {
    "$id": "#root/annotations/items/type_uri",
    "title": "Type_uri",
    "type": [
      "string",
      "null"
    ],
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
}
```

```

    "type": {
      "$id": "#root/annotations/items/type",
      "title": "Type",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "GPE"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    }
  }
}
}
}
}
}
}

```

5.2 Tag Cloud Generator Output

5.2.1 Tag Cloud Generator Output JSON example

```

{
  "ontology": "SARGA",
  "startDate": "2022-07-04T00:00:01.000Z",
  "endDate": "2022-09-06T00:00:01.000Z",
  "cloudType": 1,
  "name": "Trend analysis",
  "description": "Tag cloud filtered by category. This will show all entities of a given category together with external entities mentioned with them.",
  "data": [
    {
      "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Region",
      "type_name": "Region",
      "events": []
    },
    {
      "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
      "type_name": "Wine",
      "events": [
        {
          "label": "Viña Oria Tinto Tempranillo",
          "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#VinaOriaTintoTempranillo",
          "numMentions": 1
        },
        {
          "label": "Viñas del Vero Riesling Colección",
          "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#VinasVeroRiesling",
          "numMentions": 1
        },
        {
          "label": "El Circo. Malabarista. Macabeo",

```



```
    "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ELCircoMalabaristaMacabeo",
    "numMentions": 1
  },
  {
    "label": "Marin Tempranillo",
    "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#MarinTempranillo",
    "numMentions": 1
  }
]
},
{
  "type_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Winery",
  "type_name": "Winery",
  "events": [
    {
      "label": "Bodegas Valdovinos",
      "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Valdovinos",
      "numMentions": 1
    },
    {
      "label": "creativity",
      "item_uri": "http://wikiwiki.com/creativity",
      "numMentions": 1
    },
    {
      "label": "Bodegas Alodia",
      "item_uri": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Alodia",
      "numMentions": 1
    }
  ]
}
]
```

5.2.2 Tag Cloud Generator Output Validation Schema

```
{
  "definitions": {},
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "https://example.com/object1666108715.json",
  "title": "Root",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "ontology",
    "startDate",
    "endDate",
    "cloudType",
    "name",
    "description",
    "data"
  ]
}
```



```
],
"properties": {
  "ontology": {
    "$id": "#root/ontology",
    "title": "Ontology",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "SARGA"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "startDate": {
    "$id": "#root/startDate",
    "title": "Startdate",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "2022-07-04T00:00:01.000Z"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "endDate": {
    "$id": "#root/endDate",
    "title": "Enddate",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "2022-09-06T00:00:01.000Z"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "cloudType": {
    "$id": "#root/cloudType",
    "title": "Cloudtype",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      1
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "name": {
    "$id": "#root/name",
    "title": "Name",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "Trend analysis"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "description": {
    "$id": "#root/description",
    "title": "Description",
    "type": "string",
```



```
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "Tag cloud filtered by category. This will show all entities of a given
      category together with external entities mentioned with them."
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "data": {
    "$id": "#root/data",
    "title": "Data",
    "type": "array",
    "default": [],
    "items": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items",
      "title": "Items",
      "type": "object",
      "required": [
        "type_uri",
        "type_name",
        "events"
      ],
      "properties": {
        "type_uri": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/type_uri",
          "title": "Type_uri",
          "type": "string",
          "default": "",
          "examples": [
            "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine"
          ],
          "pattern": "^.*$"
        },
        "type_name": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/type_name",
          "title": "Type_name",
          "type": "string",
          "default": "",
          "examples": [
            "Wine"
          ],
          "pattern": "^.*$"
        }
      },
      "events": {
        "$id": "#root/data/items/events",
        "title": "Events",
        "type": "array",
        "default": [],
        "items": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/events/items",
          "title": "Items",
          "type": "object",
          "required": [
            "Label",
            "item_uri",
            "numMentions"
          ]
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

```
    ],
    "properties": {
      "label": {
        "$id": "#root/data/items/events/items/Label",
        "title": "Label",
        "type": "string",
        "default": "",
        "examples": [
          "Viña Oria Tinto Tempranillo"
        ],
        "pattern": "^.*$"
      },
      "item_uri": {
        "$id": "#root/data/items/events/items/item_uri",
        "title": "Item_uri",
        "type": "string",
        "default": "",
        "examples": [
          "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#VinaOriaTintoTempranillo"
        ],
        "pattern": "^.*$"
      },
      "numMentions": {
        "$id": "#root/data/items/events/items/numMentions",
        "title": "Nummentions",
        "type": "integer",
        "examples": [
          1
        ],
        "default": 0
      }
    }
  }
}
```

5.3 Bursty Analysis Output

5.3.1 Bursty Analysis Output JSON Example

```
{
  "startDateI": "2022-01-01T00:00:01.000Z",
  "endDateI": "2022-05-01T00:00:01.000Z",
  "startDateII": "2022-05-01T00:00:01.000Z",
  "endDateII": "2022-10-01T00:00:01.000Z",
  "eventsDown": [
    {
      "http://wikiwiki.com/auxin": 1,

```



```
"http://wikiwiki.com/deraigns": 1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/habitudes": 1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CanfraneroRose": 1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#BotijowWhite": 1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#MerlotSeleccion": 1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/outlaid": 1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/thetic": 1,
"category": "old"
},
{
"http://wikiwiki.com/auxin": 0,
"http://wikiwiki.com/deraigns": 0,
"http://wikiwiki.com/habitudes": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CanfraneroRose": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#BotijowWhite": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#MerlotSeleccion": 0,
"http://wikiwiki.com/outlaid": 0,
"http://wikiwiki.com/thetic": 0,
"category": "new"
},
{
"http://wikiwiki.com/auxin": -1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/deraigns": -1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/habitudes": -1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CanfraneroRose": -1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#BotijowWhite": -1,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#MerlotSeleccion": -1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/outlaid": -1,
"http://wikiwiki.com/thetic": -1,
"category": "difference"
},
{
"http://wikiwiki.com/auxin": -100,
"http://wikiwiki.com/deraigns": -100,
"http://wikiwiki.com/habitudes": -100,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CanfraneroRose": -100,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#BotijowWhite": -100,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#MerlotSeleccion": -100,
"http://wikiwiki.com/outlaid": -100,
"http://wikiwiki.com/thetic": -100,
"category": "percentage"
}
],
"eventsUp": [
{
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#FabulaPanizaCarinena": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LauTintoJoven": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CamposLuzViura": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LeiaCrianza": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#SantoCristo": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AltasParcelas": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ClaravalCuvee": 0,
"http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AlmonacVinoConsagrar": 0,
"category": "old"
},

```



```
{
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#FabulaPanizaCarinena": 2,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LausTintoJoven": 2,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CamposLuzViura": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LeiaCrianza": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#SantoCristo": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AltasParcelas": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ClaravalCuvee": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AlmonacVinoConsagrar": 1,
  "category": "new"
},
{
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#FabulaPanizaCarinena": 2,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LausTintoJoven": 2,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CamposLuzViura": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LeiaCrianza": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#SantoCristo": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AltasParcelas": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ClaravalCuvee": 1,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AlmonacVinoConsagrar": 1,
  "category": "difference"
},
{
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#FabulaPanizaCarinena": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LausTintoJoven": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#CamposLuzViura": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LeiaCrianza": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#SantoCristo": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AltasParcelas": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ClaravalCuvee": 100,
  "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AlmonacVinoConsagrar": 100,
  "category": "percentage"
}
]
}
```

5.4 Sentiment Aggregator output

5.4.1 Aggregator Output JSON Example

```
{
  "startDate": "2022-01-19",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23",
  "data": [
    {
      "filter": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine",
      "items": [
        {
          "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AndresMeler",
          "countries": [
            {
              "id": "BE",
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```



```
"sentiment": {
  "sentiment_score": 0,
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "negative": 0,
    "neutral": 0,
    "positive": 1
  },
  "count": 1
},
"historical": {
  "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
  "periodicity": "day",
  "aggregates": [
    {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
      "count": 1,
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
    }
  ]
}
```



```
        "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
      }
    ]
  }
},
],
"sentiment": {
  "sentiment_score": 0,
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "negative": 0,
    "neutral": 0,
    "positive": 1
  },
  "count": 1
},
"historical": {
  "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
  "periodicity": "day",
  "aggregates": [
    {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
      "count": 1,
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
    }
  ],
  "count": 0
}
```



```
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 0
        },
        "count": 0,
        "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#ClaravalTempranillo",
    "countries": [
      {
        "id": "BE",
        "sentiment": {
          "sentiment_score": 0,
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
            "neutral": 0,
            "positive": 1
          }
        },
        "count": 1
      },
      {
        "historical": {
          "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
          "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
          "periodicity": "day",
          "aggregates": [
            {
              "sentiment_score": 0,
              "sentimentCounts": {
                "negative": 0,
                "neutral": 0,
                "positive": 1
              }
            },
            {
              "count": 1,
              "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
              "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
            }
          ]
        },
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 0
        },
        "count": 0,
        "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
      }
    ],
  },
}
```



```
        {
          "sentiment_score": "NaN",
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
            "neutral": 0,
            "positive": 0
          },
          "count": 0,
          "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
          "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
        },
        {
          "sentiment_score": "NaN",
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
            "neutral": 0,
            "positive": 0
          },
          "count": 0,
          "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
          "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
        }
      ]
    },
    "sentiment": {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
      "count": 1
    },
    "historical": {
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
      "periodicity": "day",
      "aggregates": [
        {
          "sentiment_score": 0,
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
            "neutral": 0,
            "positive": 1
          },
          "count": 1,
          "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
          "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
        },
        {
          "sentiment_score": "NaN",
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
```



```
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
},
{
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
},
{
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
}
]
}
},
{
    "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#EstecilloGarnachaLegado",
    "countries": [
        {
            "id": "BE",
            "sentiment": {
                "sentiment_score": 0,
                "sentimentCounts": {
                    "negative": 0,
                    "neutral": 0,
                    "positive": 1
                },
            },
            "count": 1
        },
        "historical": {
            "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
            "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
            "periodicity": "day",
            "aggregates": [
                {
                    "sentiment_score": 0,
                    "sentimentCounts": {
```



```
        "negative": 0,  
        "neutral": 0,  
        "positive": 1  
    },  
    "count": 1,  
    "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",  
    "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"  
},  
{  
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",  
    "sentimentCounts": {  
        "negative": 0,  
        "neutral": 0,  
        "positive": 0  
    },  
    "count": 0,  
    "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",  
    "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"  
},  
{  
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",  
    "sentimentCounts": {  
        "negative": 0,  
        "neutral": 0,  
        "positive": 0  
    },  
    "count": 0,  
    "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",  
    "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"  
},  
{  
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",  
    "sentimentCounts": {  
        "negative": 0,  
        "neutral": 0,  
        "positive": 0  
    },  
    "count": 0,  
    "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",  
    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"  
}  
]  
},  
"sentiment": {  
    "sentiment_score": 0,  
    "sentimentCounts": {  
        "negative": 0,  
        "neutral": 0,  
        "positive": 1  
    },  
    "count": 1  
},  
"historical": {
```



```
"initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
"endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
"periodicity": "day",
"aggregates": [
  {
    "sentiment_score": 0,
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 1
    },
    "count": 1,
    "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
  },
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
  },
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
  },
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
  }
]
},
{
  "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#LeiaCrianza",
  "countries": [
    {
```



```
"id": "BE",
"sentiment": {
  "sentiment_score": 0,
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "negative": 0,
    "neutral": 0,
    "positive": 1
  },
},
"count": 1
},
"historical": {
  "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
  "periodicity": "day",
  "aggregates": [
    {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
    },
    "count": 1,
    "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
  ],
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
  },
  "count": 0,
  "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
},
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
  },
  "count": 0,
  "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
},
  {
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
      "positive": 0
    },
  },
}
```



```
        "count": 0,  
        "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",  
        "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"  
      }  
    ]  
  },  
  ],  
  "sentiment": {  
    "sentiment_score": 0,  
    "sentimentCounts": {  
      "negative": 0,  
      "neutral": 0,  
      "positive": 1  
    },  
    "count": 1  
  },  
  "historical": {  
    "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",  
    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",  
    "periodicity": "day",  
    "aggregates": [  
      {  
        "sentiment_score": 0,  
        "sentimentCounts": {  
          "negative": 0,  
          "neutral": 0,  
          "positive": 1  
        },  
        "count": 1,  
        "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",  
        "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"  
      },  
      {  
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",  
        "sentimentCounts": {  
          "negative": 0,  
          "neutral": 0,  
          "positive": 0  
        },  
        "count": 0,  
        "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",  
        "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"  
      },  
      {  
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",  
        "sentimentCounts": {  
          "negative": 0,  
          "neutral": 0,  
          "positive": 0  
        },  
        "count": 0,  
        "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",  
        "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"  
      }  
    ]  
  },  
}
```



```
{
  "sentiment_score": "NaN",
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "negative": 0,
    "neutral": 0,
    "positive": 0
  },
  "count": 0,
  "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
}
],
},
{
  "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#OscablancoJoven",
  "countries": [
    {
      "id": "BE",
      "sentiment": {
        "sentiment_score": 0,
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 1
        }
      },
      "count": 1
    },
    "historical": {
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
      "periodicity": "day",
      "aggregates": [
        {
          "sentiment_score": 0,
          "sentimentCounts": {
            "negative": 0,
            "neutral": 0,
            "positive": 1
          }
        }
      ],
      "count": 1,
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
    }
  ]
}
```



```
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
    }
  ]
},
"sentiment": {
  "sentiment_score": 0,
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "negative": 0,
    "neutral": 0,
    "positive": 1
  },
  "count": 1
},
"historical": {
  "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
  "periodicity": "day",
  "aggregates": [
    {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
      "count": 1,
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
```



```
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
},
{
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
},
{
    "sentiment_score": "NaN",
    "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
    },
    "count": 0,
    "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
}
]
},
{
    "filter": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Winery",
    "items": [
        {
            "id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#BodegaBioenos",
            "countries": [
                {
                    "id": "BE",
                    "sentiment": {
                        "sentiment_score": 0,
                        "sentimentCounts": {
                            "negative": 0,
                            "neutral": 0,
                            "positive": 1
                        }
                    },
                    "count": 1
                },
                "historical": {
                    "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
                    "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
```



```
    "periodicity": "day",
    "aggregates": [
      {
        "sentiment_score": 0,
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 1
        },
        "count": 1,
        "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
      },
      {
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 0
        },
        "count": 0,
        "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
      },
      {
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 0
        },
        "count": 0,
        "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
      },
      {
        "sentiment_score": "NaN",
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "negative": 0,
          "neutral": 0,
          "positive": 0
        },
        "count": 0,
        "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
        "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
      }
    ]
  },
  "sentiment": {
    "sentiment_score": 0,
    "sentimentCounts": {
      "negative": 0,
      "neutral": 0,
```



```
    "positive": 1
  },
  "count": 1
},
"historical": {
  "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
  "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00",
  "periodicity": "day",
  "aggregates": [
    {
      "sentiment_score": 0,
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 1
      },
      "count": 1,
      "initDate": "2022-01-19 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-20 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-21 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00"
    },
    {
      "sentiment_score": "NaN",
      "sentimentCounts": {
        "negative": 0,
        "neutral": 0,
        "positive": 0
      },
      "count": 0,
      "initDate": "2022-01-22 00:00:00",
      "endDate": "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
    }
  ]
}
```



```
}  
  ]  
} ]  
}
```

5.4.2 Sentiment Aggregator Validation Schema

```
{  
  "definitions": {},  
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",  
  "$id": "https://example.com/object1666109333.json",  
  "title": "Root",  
  "type": "object",  
  "required": [  
    "startDate",  
    "endDate",  
    "data"  
  ],  
  "properties": {  
    "startDate": {  
      "$id": "#root/startDate",  
      "title": "Startdate",  
      "type": "string",  
      "default": "",  
      "examples": [  
        "2022-01-19"  
      ],  
      "pattern": "^.*$"   
    },  
    "endDate": {  
      "$id": "#root/endDate",  
      "title": "Enddate",  
      "type": "string",  
      "default": "",  
      "examples": [  
        "2022-01-23"  
      ],  
      "pattern": "^.*$"   
    },  
    "data": {  
      "$id": "#root/data",  
      "title": "Data",  
      "type": "array",  
      "default": [],  
      "items": {
```



```
"$id": "#root/data/items",
"title": "Items",
"type": "object",
"required": [
  "filter",
  "items"
],
"properties": {
  "filter": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/filter",
    "title": "Filter",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#Wine"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "items": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items",
    "title": "Items",
    "type": "array",
    "default": [],
    "items": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items",
      "title": "Items",
      "type": "object",
      "required": [
        "id",
        "countries",
        "sentiment",
        "historical"
      ],
      "properties": {
        "id": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/id",
          "title": "Id",
          "type": "string",
          "default": "",
          "examples": [
            "http://www.w3.org/TR/2003/PR-owl-guide-20031209/wine#AndresMeler"
          ],
          "pattern": "^.*$"
        },
        "countries": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries",
          "title": "Countries",
          "type": "array",
```



```
"default": [],
"items": {
  "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items",
  "title": "Items",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "id",
    "sentiment",
    "historical"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "id": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/id",
      "title": "Id",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "BE"
      ],
      "pattern": "^[.*$]"
    },
    "sentiment": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment",
      "title": "Sentiment",
      "type": "object",
      "required": [
        "sentiment_score",
        "sentimentCounts",
        "count"
      ],
      "properties": {
        "sentiment_score": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/sentiment_score",
          "title": "Sentiment_score",
          "type": [
            "number",
            "null"
          ],
          "examples": [
            0
          ],
          "default": 0
        },
        "sentimentCounts": {
          "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts",
          "title": "Sentimentcounts",
          "type": "object",
          "required": [
```



```
        "negative",
        "neutral",
        "positive"
    ],
    "properties": {
        "negative": {
            "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/negative",
            "title": "Negative",
            "type": "integer",
            "examples": [
                0
            ],
            "default": 0
        },
        "neutral": {
            "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/neutral",
            "title": "Neutral",
            "type": "integer",
            "examples": [
                0
            ],
            "default": 0
        },
        "positive": {
            "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/positive",
            "title": "Positive",
            "type": "integer",
            "examples": [
                1
            ],
            "default": 0
        }
    }
},
"count": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/sentiment/count",
    "title": "Count",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
        1
    ],
    "default": 0
}
},
},
```



```
"historical": {
  "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical",
  "title": "Historical",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "initDate",
    "endDate",
    "periodicity",
    "aggregates"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "initDate": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/initDate",
      "title": "Initdate",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "2022-01-19 00:00:00"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    },
    "endDate": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/endDate",
      "title": "Enddate",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    },
    "periodicity": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/periodicity",
      "title": "Periodicity",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "day"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    },
    "aggregates": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates",
      "title": "Aggregates",
      "type": "array",
      "default": [],
      "items": {
        "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items",
```



```
"title": "Items",
"type": "object",
"required": [
  "sentiment_score",
  "sentimentCounts",
  "count",
  "initDate",
  "endDate"
],
"properties": {
  "sentiment_score": {
    "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentiment_score",
    "title": "Sentiment_score",
    "type": [
      "number",
      "null"
    ],
    "examples": [
      0
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts",
    "title": "Sentimentcounts",
    "type": "object",
    "required": [
      "negative",
      "neutral",
      "positive"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "negative": {
        "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/negative",
        "title": "Negative",
        "type": "integer",
        "examples": [
          0
        ],
        "default": 0
      },
      "neutral": {
```



```
        "$id":  
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/neutral"  
",  
        "title": "Neutral",  
        "type": "integer",  
        "examples": [  
            0  
        ],  
        "default": 0  
    },  
    "positive": {  
        "$id":  
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/positive",  
        "title": "Positive",  
        "type": "integer",  
        "examples": [  
            1  
        ],  
        "default": 0  
    }  
},  
"count": {  
    "$id":  
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/count",  
    "title": "Count",  
    "type": "integer",  
    "examples": [  
        1  
    ],  
    "default": 0  
},  
"initDate": {  
    "$id":  
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/initDate",  
    "title": "Initdate",  
    "type": "string",  
    "default": "",  
    "examples": [  
        "2022-01-19 00:00:00"  
    ],  
    "pattern": "^.*$"  
},  
"endDate": {  
    "$id":  
"#root/data/items/items/items/countries/items/historical/aggregates/items/endDate",  
    "title": "Enddate",
```



```
        "type": "string",
        "default": "",
        "examples": [
            "2022-01-20 00:00:00"
        ],
        "pattern": "^.*$"
    }
}
}
}
}
}
}
},
"sentiment": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment",
    "title": "Sentiment",
    "type": "object",
    "required": [
        "sentiment_score",
        "sentimentCounts",
        "count"
    ],
    "properties": {
        "sentiment_score": {
            "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/sentiment_score",
            "title": "Sentiment_score",
            "type": [
                "number",
                "null"
            ],
            "examples": [
                0
            ],
            "default": 0
        },
        "sentimentCounts": {
            "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts",
            "title": "Sentimentcounts",
            "type": "object",
            "required": [
                "negative",
                "neutral",
                "positive"
            ],
            "properties": {
                "negative": {
```



```
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/negative",
    "title": "Negative",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      0
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "neutral": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/neutral",
    "title": "Neutral",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      0
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "positive": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/sentimentCounts/positive",
    "title": "Positive",
    "type": "integer",
    "examples": [
      1
    ],
    "default": 0
  }
}
},
"count": {
  "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/sentiment/count",
  "title": "Count",
  "type": "integer",
  "examples": [
    1
  ],
  "default": 0
}
},
"historical": {
  "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical",
  "title": "Historical",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "initDate",
    "endDate",
    "periodicity",
    "aggregates"
  ]
}
```



```
],
"properties": {
  "initDate": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/initDate",
    "title": "Initdate",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "2022-01-19 00:00:00"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "endDate": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/endDate",
    "title": "Enddate",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "2022-01-23 00:00:00"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "periodicity": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/periodicity",
    "title": "Periodicity",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "day"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "aggregates": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates",
    "title": "Aggregates",
    "type": "array",
    "default": [],
    "items": {
      "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items",
      "title": "Items",
      "type": "object",
      "required": [
        "sentiment_score",
        "sentimentCounts",
        "count",
        "initDate",
        "endDate"
      ]
    }
  }
},
],
```



```
"properties": {
  "sentiment_score": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentiment_score",
    "title": "Sentiment_score",
    "type": [
      "number",
      "null"
    ],
    "examples": [
      0
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "sentimentCounts": {
    "$id": "#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts",
    "title": "Sentimentcounts",
    "type": "object",
    "required": [
      "negative",
      "neutral",
      "positive"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "negative": {
        "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/negative",
        "title": "Negative",
        "type": "integer",
        "examples": [
          0
        ],
        "default": 0
      },
      "neutral": {
        "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/neutral",
        "title": "Neutral",
        "type": "integer",
        "examples": [
          0
        ],
        "default": 0
      },
      "positive": {
        "$id":
"#root/data/items/items/items/historical/aggregates/items/sentimentCounts/positive",
        "title": "Positive",
        "type": "integer",
```



```
}
```

5.5 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis

5.5.1 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Output JSON Example

```
{  
  "text": "tanked tapestried overmedications fiddles entoiled zemstvo codevelopers  
blackwaters Montesierra Blanco Joven waffly chopins intransigently Viñas de Paniza  
Syrah demolishing Alto Moncayo wineries Reserva de familia uitlanders dissonantly  
upclimbs updo tels monatomic monolithic mantic generously fledglings palomino  
disbursed undervalue quinta snouting",  
  "entities": {  
    "annotations": [  
      {  
        "type": "PRODUCT",  
        "label": "Reserva de familia",  
        "sentiments": {  
          "sentiment": "positive",  
          "sentiment_weights": [  
            0.002286685397848487,  
            0.0015309401787817478,  
            0.996182382106781  
          ],  
          "sentiment_score": 0.9973257248057052,  
          "review": "{\n\"is_reference\": null, \n\"patterns\": [\n{\n\"importance\": 1.0,\n\"tokens\": [\n\"tanked\", \n\"tapestried\", (...)\n], 0.04, 0.08, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06,\n0.04, 0.05, 0.07, 0.12, 0.2, 0.47, 0.26, 0.08, 0.12, 0.12, 0.04, 0.07\n]}\n}"  
        }  
      ],  
      {  
        "type": "PRODUCT",  
        "label": "Viñas de Paniza Syrah",  
        "sentiments": {  
          "sentiment": "positive",  
          "sentiment_weights": [  
            0.004041250795125961,  
            0.004052690230309963,  
            0.9919060468673706  
          ],  
          "sentiment_score": 0.9939266722649336,  
          "review": "{\n\"is_reference\": null, \n\"patterns\": [\n{\n\"importance\": 1.0,\n\"tokens\": [\n\"tanked\", \n\"tapestried\", \n\"overmedications\", \n\"fiddles\",\n\"entoiled\", (...)\n], 0.05, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.1, 0.16, 0.43, 0.21, 0.06, 0.09,\n0.1, 0.02, 0.05\n]}\n}"  
        }  
      ]  
    }  
  }  
}
```

```
]
}
}
```

5.5.2 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Output Validation Schema

```
{
  "definitions": {},
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "$id": "https://example.com/object1666109876.json",
  "title": "Root",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "text",
    "entities"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "text": {
      "$id": "#root/text",
      "title": "Text",
      "type": "string",
      "default": "",
      "examples": [
        "tanked tapestried quinta snouting"
      ],
      "pattern": "^.*$"
    },
    "entities": {
      "$id": "#root/entities",
      "title": "Entities",
      "type": "object",
      "required": [
        "annotations"
      ],
      "properties": {
        "annotations": {
          "$id": "#root/entities/annotations",
          "title": "Annotations",
          "type": "array",
          "default": [],
          "items": {
            "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items",
            "title": "Items",
            "type": "object",
            "required": [
              "type",
              "label",
              "sentiments"
            ],
            "properties": {
              "type": {
```



```
    "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/type",
    "title": "Type",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "PRODUCT"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "label": {
    "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/Label",
    "title": "Label",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      "Reserva de família"
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  },
  "sentiments": {
    "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments",
    "title": "Sentiments",
    "type": "object",
    "required": [
      "sentiment",
      "sentiment_weights",
      "sentiment_score",
      "review"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "sentiment": {
        "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments/sentiment",
        "title": "Sentiment",
        "type": "string",
        "default": "",
        "examples": [
          "positive"
        ],
        "pattern": "^.*$"
      },
      "sentiment_weights": {
        "$id":
"#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments/sentiment_weights",
        "title": "Sentiment_weights",
        "type": "array",
        "default": [],
        "items": {
          "$id":
"#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments/sentiment_weights/items",
          "title": "Items",
          "type": "number",
          "examples": [
            0.002286685397848487
          ],
          "default": 0
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```



```
    }
  },
  "sentiment_score": {
    "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments/sentiment_score",
    "title": "Sentiment_score",
    "type": "number",
    "examples": [
      0.9973257248057052
    ],
    "default": 0
  },
  "review": {
    "$id": "#root/entities/annotations/items/sentiments/review",
    "title": "Review",
    "type": "string",
    "default": "",
    "examples": [
      {"is_reference": null, (...) 0.07}}}]
    ],
    "pattern": "^.*$"
  }
}
}
}
}
}
}
}
}
}
}
```